

D4.2 Good practice guide for the delivery of model-based climate data and services

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Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we present the results of the co-exploration process undertaken to identify the most suitable options for delivering climate information within the case studies co-developed with the ASPECT Super Users. The activities described here follow an agile, user-centric approach that allows the project to adjust as scientific developments of the ASPECT project evolve, while continuously integrating feedback from Super Users and other relevant stakeholders.

We share how our co-produced climate service prototypes are being created under the ASPECT project tailored toward the needs of users from several different sectors, including agriculture, finance, governance, emergency response and the humanitarian sector. Through this diverse group of Super Users we are supporting the needs of users from a range of technical backgrounds, from other weather and climate experts in governance through to emergency responders with no weather/climate background. This necessitates a range of different formats of climate information to help support decision-making, including improved methods and data products in collaboration with WP3, user focused methods for risk, and accessible outputs such as bulletins and websites that are decision useful for users with varying levels of technical expertise.

This deliverable also analyses some of the initial feedback collected from both Super Users and other stakeholders regarding the climate service prototypes. In collaboration with WP5, some of the prototypes (or simplified versions) are being tested through surveys designed to assess their clarity, usability, and upscaling potential.

Importantly, this deliverable also discusses the key lessons learnt across the case studies through the process of co-production. For example, one key learning is that climate information needs to be accessible and meaningful for technical and non-technical users within an organisation to effectively influence decision-making around adaptation. The deliverable concludes by providing good practice recommendations for delivering model-based climate data and services through a user-centric approach, to help support delivery in other work packages in ASPECT and beyond.

About ASPECT

ASPECT aims to set up and demonstrate a seamless climate information system with a time horizon up to 30 years and accompanied with underlying research and using climate information for sectoral applications. The project's goal is to improve existing climate prediction systems and to merge their outputs across timescales together with climate projections to unify seamless climate information as a standard for sectoral decision-making.

The project focus will be on European climate information, but we will also look where there is a wider policy interest (e.g., disaster preparedness) and in regions of European interest. We will maintain a strong link with the WCRP lighthouse activities to exploit learning for explaining and predicting earth system change. To provide a bandwidth diversity of information, the seamless climate information system will be based on multi-model climate forecasts and will build on learning from projects such as EUCP. It will align with new activities on Digital Twins within Europe, including DestinE. The seamless climate information will combine physical science aspects with those from other disciplines to ensure the information is robust, reliable, and relevant for a range of user-driven decision cases. The information package will incorporate baseline forecasts and projections (plus uncertainty), and will explore new frontiers (e.g., extremes which are of socioeconomic high-level interest).

To ensure success, the research will encompass: an understanding and attribution of various processes along timescales (such as exploring signal-to-noise ratio) and their impact on predictability, new ways of initialisation of the prediction systems, merging predictions with projections, provision of regional seamless climate information for Europe by downscaling (statistical methods, AI) and HighRes models (including convection-permitting models) and innovative post-processing method enhancing the skill and robustness of the climate forecasts.

1. Introduction

In this deliverable, we present the results of the co-exploration process undertaken to identify the most suitable options for delivering climate information within the case studies co-developed with the ASPECT Super Users.

The case studies focus on five sectors, each led by a project partner:

- **Agriculture** – Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)
- **Finance (pensions)** – Met Office
- **Governance** – Centro Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC)

- **Emergency response** – Met Office
- **Humanitarian sector (health)** – Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)

The first three Super Users from the project were involved at the proposal stage, and two additional Super Users (humanitarian and emergency response) were identified later in the project (December 2023).

The specific needs of the Super Users regarding climate information are outlined in Figure 1, and they were previously described in Deliverable 4.1.

The climate information addressed here spans time scales from the next season up to 30 years, reflecting one of the core objectives of ASPECT to bridge the gap between different prediction systems through the provision of seamless climate information. The relevant decisions of interest to the Super Users, which have been co-developed into prototype climate services, and their corresponding timescales are summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The decision-making processes and time scales of focus for each Super User.

The activities described in this deliverable are based on an agile and user centric approach, meaning that it enables the project to adapt as scientific outcomes evolve, while continuously integrating feedback from the Super Users and other relevant stakeholders. In-depth interviews were selected as the general methodological approach for the user engagement part of the ASPECT case studies, as they allow for flexible, detailed, and bilateral or multilateral (for those involving several respondents) exchanges between the climate service teams (case study leads and WP4 members) and the Super Users. Interviews have been used to assess the Super Users' experiences and interactions with the climate information

relevant to their decision-making processes. The aspects explored include user preferences related to how climate information is presented (e.g., table, chart, map), visualisation options for the different climate information displayed (e.g., type of data representation, skill, forecast categories), and preferred delivery formats (e.g., bulletins, dashboards, text descriptions, application programming interfaces, etc.), among many others. The discussions during these interviews allowed tailoring the climate service prototypes developed within task 4.2 to satisfy the requirements of each Super User.

Besides the focus on the delivery formats required by the ASPECT Super Users, this report also integrates feedback from other relevant stakeholders. In collaboration with WP5, the prototypes (or a simplified version of them) are tested through surveys dedicated to assess the understanding, usability and upscaling potential of the information, i.e. how well it travels to other users in the same sector and/or to other sectors. The feedback obtained both from the Super Users and other stakeholders regarding the climate service prototypes is analysed in this document. This analysis (of what works and not) provides a list of good practices for the delivery of model-based climate data and services that will inform developments in WPs 6 and 7, and that can be useful for the climate-adaptation community at large.

2. Different types of delivery formats

Developing a climate service involves careful consideration of various components, such as the decision context, the ecosystem of actors and co-production processes, the knowledge systems, as well as the delivery mode and evaluation of the climate service ([Doblas-Reyes et al. 2024](#)). The delivery format component involves the consideration of criteria like accessibility, following good practices in visualisation, communication & design, timeliness, and evaluation of the service (Grainger et al., 2016). There is already a body of literature on recommendations, best practices and guidance for aspects related to the delivery mode and evaluation, such as visualisation ([Terrado et al., 2022](#)), upscaling ([Guentchev et al., 2023](#)), or for targeted and specific purposes such as adaptation ([Boon et al., 2024](#)). However, a comprehensive set of guidance and good practices is still missing.

Delivery formats should ideally be developed through an iterative user-centered design approach, which integrates the understanding of the user characteristics (abilities, needs, education) and user requirements to ensure the climate information is provided in an intuitive and useful format. This method allows the user to perform work-related tasks efficiently and effectively ([Argyle et al. 2017](#)). Multiple delivery formats have been used for sharing climate information with different stakeholder groups, depending on the purpose and type of audience. Some options include application programming interfaces (APIs) to directly share data, decision support tools and dashboards, periodic bulletins, websites including text descriptions, interactive catalogues of figures, user advice/guidance, or outlook webinars where the forecasts are directly explained to the users (Figure 2).

Beyond the delivery format, critical design choices may include the selection of climate variables and/or indicators, their spatial and temporal resolution, forecasting horizon, and the timing and frequency of forecast issuance, all of which must align with users' decision-making contexts ([Manrique-Suñén et al. 2023](#)). Also the way of presenting this information is not trivial, and needs to consider the application of a user-centred design approach, using interaction in a suitable way in visualisations, paying attention to information

architecture or selecting the right type of representation (maps, graphs, etc.) and visual encoding ([Terrado et al. 2022](#); [Calvo et al. 2022](#)).

Figure 2. Examples of the different types of delivery formats of climate information for specific user applications.

3. Prototype description

3.1. Agriculture case study (led by BSC)

3.1.1. Key Background

[Codorníu](#) is the oldest wine producer in Spain. One of the most relevant wineries of Codorníu is Raïmat, which has been a pioneer in viticultural and winemaking technologies. They have a strong commitment to sustainable viticulture and respect for the land and the environment.

Codorníu is the organization that has collaborated closely with BSC in developing the ASPECT climate service prototype focused on the agricultural sector. The company has identified climate variability as a key factor influencing interannual fluctuations in grape yield and wine production. Access to reliable and timely climate information enables wineries to optimize planning and management across multiple timescales, supporting both short-term operational decisions and long-term investment strategies.

Within the ASPECT project, the agriculture case study focuses on those relevant decisions for Codorníu which could benefit from seamless climate information:

- 1. Spring Frost Protection:** Spring is the most critical period for frost risk. Even a single night with temperatures below 0 °C can severely damage the vines, destroying shoots and significantly reducing fruit yield. Seasonal climate forecasts might help determine whether management actions (such as delayed pruning to postpone bud break) can minimize frost damage. Multi-annual predictions can be also beneficial to have information on the frost occurrence in the upcoming years and support strategic investment decisions or vineyard site selection, such as implementing frost protection systems.

2. Water Management: Codorníu operates irrigated vineyards supported by water reservoirs. During drought periods, water restrictions can limit irrigation capacity and directly affect production. Hence, seasonal predictions on the drought duration might help the Super User to decide whether to adjust production expectations or source grapes from external producers. In the long term, understanding future drought trends guides crop selection decisions, encouraging the choice of varieties with lower water requirements.

3.1.2. Co-development of a climate service prototype for the wine sector

A bilateral brainstorming meeting between Codorníu and BSC was held in February 2025 to explore the different options for delivering the climate information produced within the ASPECT project. During the meeting, two main user profiles representing Codorníu emerged: a technical persona and a non-technical one. This distinction is important, as it has been discussed in Section 5.

For technical users seeking more detailed and technical information, within the company, access to an interactive web application featuring a catalogue of figures — such as forecast maps, skill maps or specific plots showing the forecast probabilities for the Raimat location — would be valuable. This resulted in the sharing of a Shiny App (https://earth.bsc.es/shiny/cdelgado_ASPECT-wine-casestudy/; credentials will be provided upon request), previously developed for project's internal purposes, with the company.

For non-technical users, a document combining maps of seasonal and decadal predictions for the upcoming months and years, together with user-tailored indicators, interpretative analysis, and practical guidance, would serve best as the primary communication tool. This resulted in the co-development of a bulletin (PDF format).

Since the Shiny app was already available (and just some maps were added following the initial brainstorming with the Super User), a co-design session to co-develop the bulletin was conducted online on March 27th, 2025. The session focused on defining the time frequency for the delivery of the bulletin, the delivery format, the climate information (i.e. indicators) to be included in it, and the options for the visualisation of climate information.

During these sessions, the Think Aloud technique was applied. This is a standard usability research method, in which users verbalize their thoughts while interacting with a product, allowing researchers to gain insight into users' reasoning, expectations, and potential usability issues (Ericsson & Simon, 1993). The technique was used to collect Codorníu's feedback and understanding of the different mock-ups, which illustrated various types of visualisations of probabilistic climate forecasts currently available in the literature. Based on the insights gained from these sessions, we were able to develop a final product tailored to the needs of Codorníu.

Bulletin frequency and timing

BSC and Codorníu discussed the different options for the release of the bulletin:

- *Option 1:* one bulletin in January-February with the climate indicators relevant for the decisions of frost and water management
- *Option 2:* Two bulletins

- Winter bulletin: climate indicators relevant for both frost and water management decisions.
- Late-spring bulletin: climate indicators relevant for water management and particularly for irrigation planning.
- *Alternative options*: Regular monthly or 3-monthly bulletins.

BSC and Codorníu agreed that having a **monthly bulletin** might be very helpful to keep the Super User engaged with the outputs of ASPECT. Some information (e.g., seasonal forecasts of frost occurrence) will not be included in some of the bulletins if not relevant/available. In such cases, this will be explicitly stated in the bulletin to ensure consistency across bulletins from different seasons.

Delivery mode

BSC proposed different options to share the bulletin:

- PDF sent by email
- Short meeting or webinar for explaining and discussing the climate information
- Both (most informative; PDF + verbal discussion of key insights)

Codorníu showed interest in receiving the bulletin via email and in the organisation a short meeting in case we have any exceptional climate event affecting their spring frost protection and water management decisions.

Visualisation options

Different mock-ups were presented to define how different aspects of climate information could be presented (a tick in the box indicates the Super Users' choice):

1. **Forecast probabilities**: climate predictions are probabilistic, so it is important to identify the best way to present the distribution of the different simulation results (ensemble members) for the given variable. Different options based on previous experiences were shown to Codorníu:
 - Most likely tercile map
 - Tercile plot
 - Probability density function
 - Most likely tercile map + tercile plot
 - Most likely tercile map + probability density function

A map for the whole area of Catalunya was considered useful for Codorníu, since apart from the Raimat region, this allows them to have strategic information from the Penedès region, where they also grow grapes. It was also agreed that bar plots on x-axis will display reference values for the variable for the normal category, so the Super User can have a better idea of what 'normal' conditions are (see example in Figure 3).

Figure 3. Example of the seasonal forecast visualisation for growing degree days. These plots are based on tercile probabilities for a specific start date: (a) map with the most likely tercile including a cross (x) where the ranked probability skill score is below 0 (no skill), (b) tercile probabilities (below normal, normal and above normal) for Raimat.

2. **Colour scales:** major climate information providers (e.g. Copernicus, NOAA, IPCC) commonly use red–blue colour scales for temperature and blue/green–brown/yellow for precipitation. These choices are based on intuitive and accessible design principles, but they may confuse users who expect consistent colors for above- and below-normal conditions across variables. These options were discussed with Codorníu (Figure 4):

- Inverted colour scales for temperature and precipitation
- Fix colour scales

For the selected option (inverted colour scales), temperature-related information is given in red for hot and in blue for cold temperatures, whereas precipitation-related information is displayed in red for dry and in blue for wet.

Questions - Colour scales

Option 1
Inverted colour scales for the 'above normal' and 'below normal' categories depending on the variable

Temperature

Precipitation

Option 2
Fix colour scales for the 'above normal' and 'below normal' categories depending on the variable

Temperature

Precipitation

Do you have any preference for colours?

Option 1
 Option 2

Figure 4. Examples of the colour scales that might be used for the most likely tercile maps. Option 1 displayed inverted colour scales for temperature and precipitation (i.e blue is used to represent high probability of below-normal temperature and above-normal precipitation). Option 2 used consistent meaning for different variables, with warm colours (orange and brown) representing above-normal conditions and cool colours (blue/green) representing below-normal temperatures.

3. **Representation of skill/forecast quality:** there are different ways to represent the forecast quality of the climate information. This information is fundamental to understand if the forecasts can provide added value to the naive forecast previously used by users (e.g. climatology, persistence, etc). Three different options were discussed for the visualisations based on maps:

- Not showing the skill information
- Adding a mask
- Stippling
- Hatching
- Other

Hatching was selected by the user, but this visualisation option has been adapted to the use of grid cells by using a cross in areas with no skill. Hatching may work better with polygons (countries, provinces, etc).

Furthermore, in internal discussions with project partners, the use of a traffic light to indicate skill was suggested, following practices from the German Weather Service ([Deutscher Wetterdienst](#), 2025), but this has not been finally included in the bulletin as this was not requested by Codorníu.

Figure 5. Legend used within the bulletin to provide information about the forecast quality.

For the integration of the forecast quality information on the bar plot, different options were discussed (Figure 6, left):

- Transparency and a label saying skill <0
- Removing the bars when the skill is <0
- Transparency + climatological probability + label skill <0
- Remove colours + climatological probability + label skill <0

4. **Performance of the prediction in the past:** Users might be interested in information about how well the predictions have performed for specific relevant past events (e.g., a spring frost episode affecting wine production). We showed Codorníu two options (Figure 6b) to visualise the probability of the tercile categories and the observed category for the past:

- Heatmap with probabilities
- Heatmap with forecast category (below normal, normal, above normal)

Additional issues affecting only the display of decadal predictions were discussed. These included Codorníu's preference for having information for the next years individually (2025 and 2026) instead of aggregated in the 2025-26 average.

Figure 6. a) Examples of the mock-ups shown during the co-design process with Codorníu to identify the most suitable format for the visualisation of the skill in the bar plot. b) Examples of the mock-ups shown during the co-design process with Codorníu to identify the most suitable format for the visualisation and the agreement between the forecasts in the past and the observations (bottom panel).

3.1.3. Bulletin: content and structure

Based on the feedback from Codorníu, a bulletin has been designed to provide a summary of the most relevant information to support key vineyard management decisions for the company: frost protection and water management. The bulletin includes seasonal and decadal predictions, offering information at different time horizons that can be used to guide

operational and strategic planning. This first version of the bulletin provides climate information based on state-of-the-art climate prediction systems at seasonal and decadal timescales. A version of the bulletin including seamless climate information generated in ASPECT (either using temporal merging or extended predictions or both) will be produced once the results are available. In addition, Codorníu showed interest in having climate information with higher resolution than the original resolution from the climate models. Hence, these downscaled predictions will be included in future versions of the bulletin. The challenges of producing high-resolution climate information have been further discussed in Section 5.1.

Figure 7. Overview of the first version of the bulletin co-designed with Codorníu for the April-September season in 2025. The full version of the bulletin has been included in the [ANNEX](#).

The bulletin is structured in the following sections:

1. **Bulletin overview:** This first page provides an introduction to the bulletin, with a concise summary of the expected conditions at both seasonal and decadal time scales for the two decisions: frost protection and water management. In this way, the user can have a quick understanding of how climate conditions might look like in the next months and years. This page also includes a link to the ASPECT website as well as contact information, ensuring users know where to reach out for questions, clarifications, or feedback on the forecasts and their application.
2. **User guide.** The second page provides guidance on how to read and interpret the figures and indicators shown in the bulletin. It is intended to help users understand the forecast products and it has three subsections:
 - *Indicator definitions.* Different climate indicators have been selected based on their relevance to guide frost protection and water management decisions. The selection of indicators was jointly agreed between Codorníu and BSC, based on the needs of the Super User and the capacity of the research

institution to provide the information. Information on how they have been calculated and the assumptions taken is included here.

- *Time scales*: The preliminary version of the bulletin includes two types of predictions: seasonal predictions, which provide climate information useful for the next six months, and decadal predictions providing climate information for the next years.
 - *Legends*: Contain a description of how to interpret the different maps and plots. This includes the predicted tercile plots, which use different categories and colours to indicate below normal, normal and above normal conditions, and the probabilities given to each tercile. The legend also includes information on how to interpret the quality of the prediction.
3. **Frost protection**. The following pages contain information on the indicators relevant for spring frost (i.e., frost days and growing degree days). These indicators are calculated for March and April, both at seasonal and decadal time scales, since these are the months in which temperatures below zero can damage the plant. Each forecast product is displayed as a map showing information on the most likely tercile, the prediction quality, a tercile plot and a short description.
 4. **Water management**. Information is also given for the indicators relevant for water management. This includes average temperature, total precipitation, the standardized precipitation and evapotranspiration index (SPEI) - that provides information on drought -, heatwaves, and growing degree days. These indicators are provided for the plant growing season from April to September, both at seasonal and decadal time scales. Each forecast product is displayed as a map showing information on the most likely tercile, the prediction quality, a tercile plot and a short description.

3.2. Humanitarian case study (led by BSC)

3.2.1. Key Background

Save the Children International (SCI) is an international non-governmental organization that works to improve the lives of children by providing humanitarian aid, supporting their health, education, and safety, and advocating for their rights. Founded in 1919 in the UK, it is now a global movement that works in 115 countries to support children's development and protection, both during crises and on a long-term basis.

The main objective of the humanitarian case study in ASPECT, is to provide SCI with tailored climate information to support anticipatory action against malnutrition. As the organisation works in various regions of Africa, two case studies have been identified in Malawi and Niger with the objective to assist the national governments to plan nutrition sensitive anticipatory actions that help reduce the population's vulnerability to food insecurity.

The affordability of a nutritious diet has been identified as a proxy for food (in)security. For a specific consumption year, the affordability of a nutritious diet is assessed by comparing the food (crops and livestock) and income required for a household with the food and income deficit that a household suffers after a climate shock, e.g. drought (Figure 8). Climate

predictions provided by BSC give information about the climate conditions expected for the rainy season as well as the whole consumption year. At the short and medium time scales, this information allows Save the Children to plan for anticipatory action, identifying appropriate interventions to ensure that households can cope with climate shocks, meaning they can survive and maintain basic expenditures. Over longer time scales (decadal) this information is needed to develop nutrition-sensitive adaptation plans. This information can also guide strategic agricultural decisions, including crop selection and diversification. For example, if drought conditions are expected, promoting drought-tolerant or low-water-demand crops may strengthen resilience and reduce future food and income deficits.

Overall, the integration of climate information into SCI's anticipatory frameworks enables proactive decision-making, supporting early action and optimal allocation of humanitarian resources to mitigate the impacts of climate shocks on vulnerable populations.

Figure 8. Conceptual illustration of households' affordability of a nutritious diet. Source: Save the Children International

3.2.2. Climate information

BSC has evaluated the forecast quality of multi-annual predictions of mean and extreme temperatures, precipitation, and drought indicators (the Standardised Precipitation-Evapotranspiration Index, SPEI, at different accumulation periods) in Malawi and Niger. The climate predictions have been statistically downscaled and aggregated at livelihood zone levels to align with SCI's operational framework and data needs. The study focuses on the rainy seasons of each country (November to April in Malawi, and June to September in Niger). For Niger, aggregations have been carried out for the dry season (October to May) and consumption year (October to September), which was requested by the Super User to better reflect the food security calendar. Additionally, seamless seasonal-to-decadal predictions of ENSO have been also included in this case study due to its teleconnection with regional climate conditions in both countries.

The forecast products include multi-model ensemble predictions, individual forecast systems, and reference forecasts such as climatology and persistence, used in cases where dynamical models show limited skill. The forecasts cover lead years 1, 2, and 3, thus offering information at timescales relevant for early planning and multi-annual resilience strategies.

Three different delivery formats are being considered to distribute the climate information co-developed with SCI. These options combine interactive tools and static, user-friendly products to ensure that climate information is both technically robust and operationally usable, supporting the co-production of actionable climate services:

- An **R Shiny App** has been developed to facilitate access and visualisation of the climate predictions (credentials will be provided upon request). The app provides interactive access to the prediction outputs and their skill assessments, allowing SCI technical staff and project partners to explore the complete dataset. This tool primarily targets technical users within SCI and project partners, enabling detailed forecasts exploration and assessment of forecast quality. Figure 9 shows examples of the visualisation products that can be accessed through the App.

Figure 9. Example of forecast quality maps that can be found in the R Shiny App. Multi-model forecast quality for the forecast year 1 over the livelihood zones of Malawi (left) and Niger (right) for predictions of temperature (top) and SPEI (bottom) during the rainy seasons. The quality is estimated with the anomaly correlation coefficient (ACC) during the 1961-2024 period using the ERA5-Land reanalysis as the reference dataset.

- A **climate bulletin** summarising the most relevant forecasts for the upcoming rainy season will be the final user-oriented product selected by the Super User. The structure and content of the bulletin are currently being co-designed with SCI to ensure alignment with their information needs and decision-making timelines. The bulletin is intended to summarise the most relevant climate information in a concise, interpretable, and decision-oriented format, making it more suitable for non-technical users and field staff involved in anticipatory action and programme planning. The choice of this format was based on feedback from both SCI, who valued the clarity, accessibility, and visual design of the bulletin developed for the case study on the agriculture sector. Its structure is expected to favour the integration into SCI's existing reporting and communication channels.
- In addition, **training sessions** and forecast briefings are being discussed with the Super User for Q1 and Q2 2026, which will include interpretation of the forecasts and their quality, with focus on the new seamless predictions produced during the project. These sessions will aim to strengthen SCI's understanding and use of climate predictions for anticipatory nutrition interventions, fostering long-term sustainability and ownership of climate services within the humanitarian sector. The need for training is discussed further along with other key lessons learnt from the climate service development process in Section 5.

3.3. Finance (pensions) case study (led by Met Office)

3.3.1. Key Background

User engagement has revealed that the financial sector is currently at a very early stage in its understanding of climate change risks to existing and future investment decisions. The pension sector generally has a low appreciation of the physical risk associated with climate change in their investments, and we identified an opportunity for ASPECT to contribute to systemic change of the sector toward sustainability and steering economic activities toward socially beneficial outcomes.

Risk analysis by pension funds typically does not adequately consider current or future physical climate risks. For example, the Pensions Regulator in the UK has revealed that quantitative risk analysis in climate disclosures [is rare](#). The Pensions Regulator (UK) also highlights that many trustees achieve only [minimum compliance](#) with environmental social governance duties, with experts warning of a [looming climate change related mispricing crisis](#). To this end, pension schemes that cannot act to protect pensions from climate risk have been warned they should [quit the market](#).

However, in terms of decision-making and support, user engagement reveals concern around a lack of **transparent, robust and decision-useful** tools for climate risk assessment for the financial sector. This potentially ultimately hinders pension trustees and asset managers from making climate informed decisions relating to adaptation. Effective risk management of physical climate risks requires deep climate expertise. While there are products on the market, there is concern that users of these products may not have sufficient information about whether the models and outputs are scientifically robust and suitable for the decision context, or if the models may not provide enough information about the range of possible climate futures.

Our understanding of the decision-making context of pension funds has identified that to **drive change** in the sector, we should design a climate service prototype which is effective in revealing the potential **underestimation** of **physical and financial** risk carried by pension funds who are not incorporating future climate information into their investment decision making. This can then incentivise and empower trustees of pension funds globally to identify which investments are less exposed to climate risks or more resilient to the impacts of climate change. Our aim was for this to help create **change in the market by raising climate risk awareness** with these investors, who have the power to influence asset managers across a wide range of investment types.

3.3.2. Pensions sector personas

The climate service prototype for the pensions sector developed under ASPECT consists of different parts, each tailored to different user personas that we have identified within the pensions sector (see Figure 10).

Figure 10. Different personas that we are supporting in the pensions sector through the different products we are developing as part of this climate service prototype.

Our principal Super User has been [Professor Iain Clacher](#), who is a pensions expert at the University of Leeds and a member of the [Centre for Greening Financial Investments](#) (a UK based research initiative created to accelerate the adoption and use of climate and environmental data and analytics by financial institutions internationally). Our aim working with an intermediary who can provide insight across the sector has been to produce sector relevant products that are useful to a wide range of financial actors, cognisant of the scalability aims of the wider ASPECT project.

Ultimately, we are trying to help the financial sector leverage change in the pensions sector through providing pension trustees with appropriate climate information to incentivise their push toward quantitative climate risk assessments for their portfolios. Therefore we have developed a **method** for quantifying physical and financial risk from climate impacts, and the details of this technical development are intended for a third persona working in quantitative risk assessment in a financial analytics team or a climate services provider.

As part of this prototype climate service we have developed several prototype products as follows.

3.3.3. Product #1: Website

Given the lack of prior climate knowledge by many decision makers in the pensions sector, it was critical that there was an output from the project which was steered toward **pension fund trustees with little climate background**, that would motivate them to further consider physical climate risk.

We therefore designed a short **website** (Figure 11) aimed at pension trustees or others in the financial sector without much prior climate knowledge. The website explains how climate change can increase financial losses in portfolios and motivates trustees to consider physical climate risks in their climate adaptation decisions around existing investments, or climate risk assessment of future investments. Specifically, we aimed to create a concise, user-friendly website that introduces the impacts of extreme weather (specifically, heavy rainfall and associated flooding) on potential financial losses from damage to building level assets in pension portfolios. It also explains how and why further climate change is likely to increase losses in portfolios in the future through changes to this hazard. The product is designed to provide some education around the complex considerations of using seamless climate information for this purpose, helping raise awareness and encouraging further quantitative risk assessment.

Accessibility: The website is structured to be easily navigable for those without a technical background. The website has been designed with accessibility in mind and considering responsive design, ensuring that it is usable on different types of devices (e.g., computer and mobile) and different browsers. It is also accessible using different inputs, e.g., mouse, keyboard, trackpad.

There are several advantages to providing information on a website over a document such as a .pdf. These include:

- The design elements of a website can make the information more appealing and engaging for the reader.
- Websites provide improved accessibility on multiple devices over .pdf formats. For example, some reasons why the UK Government advocates for information in websites rather than .pdf form is outlined in [this blog post](#).
- Websites are generally better for users with disabilities – for example, images with alt-text so that screen readers can share the visual information with blind users, and users can change font sizes and contrast.
- Website analytics can be tracked.
- Websites are more likely to be found and indexed by search engines, and documents such as .pdfs on the internet may not be captured accurately in the training of large language models. Therefore, websites are likely to have further reach.

Access: The current version is available at:
<https://apps.copernicus-climate.eu/aspect-pensions/>.

The content of the website was developed by the Met Office, but the website itself was developed by ASPECT partner ECMWF.

Pensions - website

<https://apps.copernicus-climate.eu/aspect-pensions/>

Website to share key information with decision makers in the pensions sector, i.e. pensions trustees.

Version 1 includes an example from an early version of method, within 10 minutes of accessible, educational content to help **raise awareness of physical risk** and help **educate about use of seamless climate information**.

Aim to provide useful context that helps trustees in discussions with climate service providers who they might employ to provide risk assessment products.

Aimed at: Pensions Trustee

Responsible for risk to pension funds.

Principal aim of 'prototype' is to educate around physical climate risk, leveraging societal change by encouraging trustee to take decision to further assess climate risk quantitatively.

Climate Service Prototype for the Pensions Sector

"Climate change can impact a wide range of pension fund investments. ASPECT can provide improved climate information to better understand these risks enabling better risk management and support effective investment decision making."

Professor Iain Clacher
Pensions expert, University of Leeds & Centre for Greening Financial Investments
ASPECT Super User

ASPECT

Scroll down to explore

Figure 11. A summary of the website part of the climate service prototype.

In line with best practice around climate service, our product development was informed by the principles of user centred design. For example, we identified we needed to create an output for trustees that could be **rapidly digested**, that was **relevant** and **understandable**, rather than deeply focussed on physical science data or focussed on demonstrating the detail of novel technical advancements. Figure 12 outlines some of the requirements for the format of the product aimed at pension trustees that we had identified.

Our climate service prototype is principally focussed on an **early decision in a climate risk assessment journey** – to take further action toward more quantitative risk assessment for individual and bespoke cases. Therefore, assuming the technical capacity to interpret complex outputs from a range of data sources is not appropriate for pension trustees and asset managers, so our aim was to produce a website that is as straightforward and understandable as possible.

Figure 12. A summary of considerations around the format designed for pensions trustees.

3.3.4. Product #2: Risk Methodology (Commercial property damage from extreme rainfall)

A principal aim of the financial case study was to provide the pensions sector, and potentially a broader range of the financial sector, with transparent, robust and decision-useful tooling for assessing physical climate risk in financial terms. Based on user engagement with our Super User partner and other financial sector actors, we have created a pragmatic method for assessing financial risk to commercial property portfolios which can be used across any region of Europe (see Figure 13 for a summary). We are designing this to be useful for pensions and other finance sector applications as damage to property assets is a potentially significant physical climate risk to any portfolio of property assets.

Summary of method:

We use rainfall data to determine an element of physical climate risk, using flood map information together with flood depth-damage curves and exposure information about commercial property to estimate risk. We use state-of-the-art statistical techniques to combine this information in a robust way, and we convert this into financial terms using a metric of interest to the financial sector, Expected Annual Damage (€). This is critical for relevance to the sector because it translates climate data on a hazard to user-relevant financial risk information.

Access

The approach is comprehensively documented in a forthcoming publication (Dawkins *et al.*, in preparation) which will be published under open access.

Key aims of the publication:

- To provide a method to explore idealised flood risk to property assets, which can be applied to different datasets and time periods.
- To provide a demonstration of the method using fully open-source information and data.
- To highlight how physical climate risk from extreme rainfall is a concern for commercial property assets in the current climate and increases in future climate.
- To explore potential actions that can be taken to reduce risk: e.g. investing in adaptation.
- To encourage the pension sector to consider climate risk in their investments.
- To encourage investment in adaptation to build climate resilience.

Addressing the seamless timescales of ASPECT

There is a need for pension funds to both assess the inherent risks (climate and otherwise) of investments they hold currently as well as any new investments pension funds are asked to make now and in the future. By better assessing and managing these risks, pension funds will be better able to achieve sustained long-term income from such investments to ensure they can meet their legal obligation to pay pensions on time, in full, as they fall due. From the perspective of climate variability and change, this means that the time scales of interest span the whole range considered by ASPECT and beyond as pension liabilities extend far into the future, with promises being made today having a lifespan of well over 50 years.

Therefore, the method is designed to be able to utilise different types of climate information (including present day climate information, present day/near term climate predictions, climate projections, or temporally merged combinations of prediction and projection information). It can also be used to better understand present day climate risk by using large ensembles of prediction hindcasts such as those provided under the Decadal Climate Prediction Project as well as ASPECT (often referred to as an UNSEEN approach e.g. [Thompson et al. 2017](#)). Large prediction ensembles can potentially also be used to assess changing risk in the near-term future. However, these data are currently available at coarse resolution and are not consistent in their skill for extreme rainfall across Europe. This is an area of continuing research across climate science and services; more user-relevant climate information is required together with robust recommendations around the use of these complex data sets in different contexts. This is discussed further along with other key lessons learnt from the climate service development process in Section 5.

In our initial work developing the method and for demonstration, we have utilised dynamically downscaled climate projection data across Europe to assess financial risk across diverse and geographically widespread examples of randomised synthetic (invented) investment portfolios in the climate of the recent past and the climate of the near future (next 30 years).

Figure 13. A summary of the hazard to financial risk methodology (Dawkins, Garry, Bernie *et al.*, in prep).

Audience

While the method is not likely to be directly used by trustees themselves, this methodology supports those who will be contracted to provide risk assessments to pension funds. Therefore, this method is aimed at analytics teams in finance or climate service providers who require technical detail around model data and information so they can produce comprehensive risk assessments for decision-making. A key feature of our paper is that an open discussion accompanying the method around the caveats provides scientific transparency and robustness that can also help analysts and trustees in conversations around interpretation and implications for decision-making. The method can potentially be used by private sector consultancies with less prior expertise in this area and this would provide a good starting point for climate service providers to consider more bespoke solutions, with comprehensive and transparent provision of caveats and limitations of the method.

Although some climate service providers do already provide climate risk assessment products to the financial sector, our user engagement indicates concern that products provided for the financial sector may not always be scientifically transparent, appropriate or robust. There are a range of reasons for this which include commercial sensitivity by necessity hindering transparency, but also different methods, data, treatment of uncertainties and consideration of the range of possible futures (e.g., [Bingler et al. 2022](#), [Hain et al. 2022](#), [Hoehn et al. 2025](#)). These caveats and limitations are important to discuss in publicly funded research to support decision-making from climate information and empower financial decision makers to ask appropriate questions of climate service providers about suitable methods for risk assessment and to aid in the interpretation of results for decision-making.

3.3.5. Product #3: Training on utilising decadal prediction data in a financial sector hackathon

Purpose: The Met Office have worked with colleagues at the University of Leeds, including our pensions Super User Professor Iain Clacher, to collaborate with another part of the financial sector with similar needs, the insurance sector (here, specifically reinsurance). The hackathon included a range of potential users of climate information from the research community as well as industry sector analysts. The public website for the hackathon is accessible [here](#), and an ASPECT write-up about the event is provided [here](#). Alongside providing steering input into this cross-research and industry initiative, ASPECT provided guidance on the use of decadal climate simulations—currently a relatively underused resource in climate services and industry. As prediction model data are not straightforward to use in a meaningful way, explainers and training to help technical users with analysing and interpreting these data are an important part of providing climate services (especially for providers with a public interest mandate such as national meteorological services).

Format: A presentation with some key information to help practitioners new to using decadal prediction information, along with access information to the latest generation of publicly available decadal prediction simulations.

Access: A slide deck specific to the data being provided at the hackathon was produced and delivered to attendees in the [Onboarding session](#) before the hackathon. These [slides](#) were made available for attendees of the hackathon to keep. A more general version of the slide deck may be made available on the ASPECT website for other users.

3.4 Emergency response case study (led by Met Office)

3.4.1. Key Background

ASPECT [recruited the British Red Cross](#) as a Super User at the very end of 2023. Initial user engagement in 2024 comprised discussions with the UK Climate Adaptation lead, the UK Climate Adaptation Group and the Strategic Insight & Foresight analytics team.

In September 2024, the UK Climate Adaptation Lead left and then there was a period of restructuring within the organisation, so a replacement was not immediately hired into that post. Although we had continued to have useful conversations and co-production of our work in the interim, this was a significant period of the ASPECT project where we did not have a contact in strategic leadership of climate related planning within the organisation. This reflects one challenge regarding user engagement on fixed term research projects, as organisations on both sides inevitably face staff changes and organisational changes. This is especially true when an organisation realises that embedding climate consideration into decision making might need existing organisational structures to change. See Section 5 for further discussion around lessons learnt during the co-production process.

During this period (late 2024 and the first half of 2025), we were able to continue our work, supported by an established relationship between the Met Office and British Red Cross.

ASPECT focussed on delivering co-produced training and drafting an initial version of a prototype website based on our user engagement in 2024.

Ultimately a new post, Climate Adaptation and Resilience Manager, was created, with the person in this role responsible for embedding climate within resilience planning in the organisation, with a remit overseeing the UK. In July 2025, we were quickly able to connect with the Climate Adaptation and Resilience Manager, to continue co-production through the rest of 2025.

3.4.2. Key organisational context

Through user engagement, we learned that the British Red Cross has strategic insights teams with strong technical expertise, focused on supporting organisational decision-making and addressing the impacts of climate on emergency response. There is a growing awareness of climate-change related increases in weather extremes at the British Red Cross, facilitated by, e.g., the Climate Action Task Force and work of the Climate Adaptation Lead during 2022-2024, alongside the work of the Red Cross Red Crescent Climate Centre.

Therefore, at a leadership level, the British Red Cross are already supported with climate information guided by their Climate Risk Assessment. There is concern about the increase in extreme heat events in the UK, particularly the effects of heatwaves on vulnerable groups. The organisation typically responds to flooding but climate-informed staff and volunteers understand the potentially significant implications of an increasing number of heat-related emergency responder callouts, alongside other related hazards such as fire. Understanding hazard combined with vulnerability and exposure (risk) is particularly important, as emergency responders need to prioritise vulnerable people who are most acutely affected by extreme heat.

The British Red Cross are at an early stage of systematically building climate-informed decision making into their planning, but there is a clear aim to build this through the organisation. They are keen to engage operational managers and emergency responders to ensure buy-in and participation in climate resilience and adaptation planning and delivery.

Red Cross Red Crescent Climate Centre and the British Red Cross Climate Hub already provide educational climate content and information on extreme weather risks. An important feature of this information is that it highlights relevance to the decision-making context using stories from past events. In the emergency response context, personal stories and lived experiences are key for effectively communicating information to responders.

Some responders may have very limited or misinformed climate knowledge, affecting their understanding of how climate change will impact response operations. They may also be supportive of wider climate action, but do not appreciate how this is relevant to their roles. This is a particular concern for heat, which is often dismissed as a hazard in the UK. The British Red Cross expects that climate sensitive decisions will increasingly need to be made throughout the organisation at a range of levels - e.g. around supplies, recruitment, workwear, rest centres.

3.4.3. Key outcomes from user engagement for product design

The theory of change (problem statement) that we are trying to address is summarised as follows. The British Red Cross faces **challenges in embedding climate resilience** planning across the organization due to **limited (or potentially misinformed)** climate knowledge, **ability to access appropriate data and information quickly** as well as **link its relevance to operational decisions** around emergency response and future planning.

Through our work, we identified that ASPECT could play a valuable role in supporting climate-informed decision-making by offering targeted training and educational resources seamlessly across the seasonal to climate timescales. These materials are designed to help emergency responders access relevant climate information, including insights from cutting-edge tools such as the Met Office's Local Authority Climate Service and the ASPECT funded ERA Explorer developed by ASPECT partner ECMWF. Critically, it was also identified that it was important to provide resources that help responders understand why climate extremes (specifically heat) are relevant to the types of decisions that responders in the British Red Cross need to make.

We identified through the user engagement process that the information needed to be high level and clear to a range of people with little or no climate background at the organisation. Emergency responders are typically very socially motivated people with a desire to help, but they want to focus on their practical tasks rather than trying to analyse lots of complex climate information to understand what it might mean for their roles. Therefore, it would likely be important to highlight the relevance to practical emergency responder decision making within the British Red Cross through examples for the climate service prototype to be successful. Other key learnings from the user-engagement and co-development processes are discussed later in Section 5 of this deliverable.

Our climate service prototype for British Red Cross has comprised of two interlinked and co-designed elements described in the following two sections, specifically:

- in-person training sessions,
- website.

3.4.4. Product #1: Training around interpreting and accessing seamless climate information for emergency responders and operational managers within the British Red Cross

We developed **training material** in co-production with British Red Cross staff during the spring period of 2025. This training was delivered in-person at the British Red Cross National Emergency Response Group meeting in Birmingham (UK) in March 2025 (in partnership with a Met Office Civil Contingency Advisor).

The aims of the workshop session were to:

- Refresh understanding and application of Met Office resources for UK emergency managers;
- Integrate both British Red Cross Strategic Insight and Met Office expertise and resources into operational planning for Summer 2025.

We co-produced the training materials to provide the material at an appropriate level, covering topics of relevance and ensuring the sessions were engaging.

The sessions included:

- an introduction to interpreting seasonal forecasts ([link to slides](#)),
- a brief introduction session to introduce the Local Authority Climate Service (a Met Office climate service available to access climate model information, including on extreme metrics, at the local scale without technical expertise), followed by a training exercise to give responders hands-on experience accessing the Local Authority Climate Service Climate Explorer website ([link to exercise](#)).

3.4.5. Product #2: Website for emergency responders and operational managers within the British Red Cross

We have built on the initial training provided by co-producing a [website](#)¹ for emergency response staff and volunteers at the British Red Cross, who respond to heatwaves or might in future. We aim to help support **climate informed thinking through the community resilience** operations of the British Red Cross, aiding **climate adaptation**.

Figure 14. An image of the top of the [website created for emergency responders within the British Red Cross](#) to learn about how understanding extreme heat might impact decision making for emergency responders, and how to access seamless climate information.

Overview:

¹ <https://apps.copernicus-climate.eu/aspect-humanitarian/>

- **Format:** A user-friendly website (Figure 14).
- **Accessibility:** The website is structured to be easily navigable for those without a technical background.
- **Access:** The current version of the website is available publicly at:
<https://apps.copernicus-climate.eu/aspect-humanitarian>.

The website content provides more information across the seamless timescale and explores how the information is relevant to the British Red Cross decision making context in more detail. It aims to help raise awareness around the impacts of extreme weather (specifically, extreme heat) on vulnerable people, and provides educational information at an appropriate level around seamless climate information. The tool also provides links and support to help find additional information and data when required. It is a resource that can be repeatedly accessed, to support climate risk assessment, decision-making and adaptation as iterative and on-going processes, and helping to support the Super User aim to embed climate informed decision-making across all resilience and preparedness work.

The website has several key objectives aligned with the ASPECT project:

- provide a **trusted source** and **signpost** to **existing user friendly** and **reliable sources of seamless climate data and information**,
- help staff to **access** and **interpret** seamless climate information,
- expand understanding of how **seamless climate data and information might be used in practical ways for seamless timescale decision making around climate adaptation within the organisation**, as the British Red Cross begins to embed climate-informed thinking within community resilience planning.

Personas

Together with the Climate Adaptation and Resilience Manager at the British Red Cross, we identified several **personas** within the British Red Cross who we were aiming to help support. We have then been able to consider the aims of the website tool for each persona, and consider what features are important for each persona. This has helped us in ensuring the design of the website tool is appropriate and usable during day-to-day operations.

An overview of these personas is shown in Figure 15, with more details about the aims and necessary features for each responder provided in Annex 8.2.

Figure 15. An overview of five personas identified at the British Red Cross.

Accessibility

We determined that an accessible, easy-to-access and informative product design was important for the British Red Cross (see following section for more information about personas). As for the Pensions website, a website is chosen over a static document format (such as .pdf) for several reasons, which we do not repeat here for brevity.

ECMWF have designed the website with accessibility in mind and considering responsive design, ensuring that it is usable on different types of device (computer and mobile) and different browsers. The website is also accessible using different inputs, e.g., mouse, keyboard, trackpad.

We can embed **video format** material within the website, which is particularly desirable for providing easily accessible content for non-climate specialists. At the time of writing, the video content on the website is minimal, using existing Met Office relevant video content only, but during the remainder of the project, we plan to expand the video content offering.

This would further **improve the accessibility** of the website. By creating accessible content, we support people who are differently abled, for example, with impaired vision, motor difficulties, deafness or impaired hearing or cognitive impairments.

We also recognise at the Met Office that accessible content can also help people with slow internet connections, in busy or loud environments, and who are time-poor and in a rush. Accessibility improves content for everyone, but in the context of the British Red Cross, accessibility is also a vital feature of the website as emergency responders may fulfil some or all these categories.

3.5. Governance case study (led by CMCC)

3.5.1. Key Background

The background of the case study relies on various European directives that help EU Member States to implement actions in terms of climate-adaptation strategy and plan. First of all, the EU Climate Law ([Regulation 2021/1119](#)) which requires development and implementation of a national adaptation plan in case of extreme and adverse weather conditions. Another example would be the international standard *ISO 14091:2021 – Adaptation to climate change: Guidelines on vulnerability, impacts and risk assessment* which gives a robust methodological framework for assessing climate risks, trying to study vulnerabilities and designing effective adaptation actions. Since adaptation planning must comply with different policies, climate-risk assessments can be produced in many forms. They may rely on single indicators or more complex indices, often involving predictions and projections of future conditions, examine long-term trends, or integrate social, economic and environmental analyses that shed light on broader climate impacts.

Super User

In the governance case study, the **Super User** is **ARPAE** (Agenzia Regionale per la Prevenzione, l’Ambiente e l’Energia dell’Emilia-Romagna), which is a research-oriented public agency with a longstanding track record in developing statistical downscaling methods, climate predictions, and climate projections to inform and support regional policy and planning. Specifically, **ARPAE** is a public research body established by the region Emilia-Romagna to provide scientific and technical expertise for environmental protection, sustainable development, and energy policy. Its activities range from monitoring air, water, soil, and biodiversity, to supporting renewable energy and energy-efficiency initiatives, and offering technical guidance to public administrations and private organisations. Over the years, to assist planning and decision-making by the Emilia-Romagna Region, **ARPAE** has developed statistical downscaling tools of various degrees of complexity and applied to different climate predictions and projections, which emerge as central for climate adaptation.

ARPAE is represented by the person of the Head of the *Climatology and Long-Term Forecasting Unit* within the *Climate Observatory Service* of ARPAE, operating inside the *Hydro-Meteo-Climate Structure* and its thematic departments. Her role places her at the centre of regional climate knowledge production, long-term climate prediction, and technical support to public authorities. As the designated Super User for the governance case study, she represents a highly specialised institutional profile, deeply embedded in the region’s climate-innovation ecosystem. In addition to that, it’s also important to highlight the Emilia-Romagna status in Europe, which positions itself as one of Europe’s region leading climate-innovation hubs. Inevitably, the Super User engaged in the Governance Case study operates within an inherently technical environment. This explains why this case study naturally involves references to technical modelling, scientific datasets, monitoring frameworks, and advanced climate-service products: these are precisely the tools and formats required by ARPAE to fulfil its mandate. Throughout the ASPECT project, we have maintained **ongoing exchanges and co-production activities** with the Head of the *Climatology and Long-Term Forecasting Unit* as representative of ARPAE. During 2025, we conducted **multiple online calls and collaborative meetings** with all members of the Governance case study—discussing user needs, validating prototypes, and ensuring that the

climate-service outputs are fully aligned with the operational and strategic requirements of regional governance actors.

Based on this, the Emilia-Romagna Region (Figure 16) has identified two priority climate challenges:

Figure 16. Administrative provinces of Emilia-Romagna

- 1) **Extreme heat** has become one of the defining climate challenges for Emilia-Romagna. Summers that were once punctuated by a few isolated hot days are now marked by long, persistent heatwaves that settle over the Po Valley and linger, sometimes for weeks. The region’s geography does not help: the flat basin traps warm air, slows ventilation and prevents nighttime temperatures from dropping, creating a suffocating heat burden that accumulates day after day. Cities like Bologna, Modena and Ferrara experience the strongest impacts. Their dense built environments amplify temperatures through the urban heat-island effect, turning already hot days into episodes of extreme discomfort and, at times, severe health risk. The combination of heat, humidity and stagnant air affects vulnerable populations first—older adults, people with chronic illnesses, and workers exposed outdoors—but the consequences ripple across the entire regional system. Hospitals face increased admissions, energy demand for cooling spikes, and agricultural landscapes struggle under the double pressure of heat and water scarcity. Rivers that once buffered the region’s climate are less able to do so as summer flows diminish, while dry soils and stressed vegetation increase the risk of wildfires in the Apennines and foothill areas. The heatwaves of recent years—especially in 2022 and 2023—have shown how extreme heat has shifted from an occasional meteorological anomaly to a structural feature of the regional climate.

- 2) **Severe rainfall events** have become a defining feature of Emilia-Romagna’s changing climate, revealing the region’s growing vulnerability to intense, short-duration downpours as well as prolonged, widespread precipitation. When these systems settle over the Po Valley, they often encounter saturated soils, impermeable urban surfaces, and an already fragile hydraulic balance—conditions that amplify both flood risk and the destructive potential of runoff. In recent years, several episodes have demonstrated how quickly the situation can escalate. Intense convective storms can unleash extraordinary amounts of rain in just a few hours, overwhelming drainage networks in cities like Bologna, Cesena, Forlì, Modena and Ravenna. Streets turn into channels, underpasses fill rapidly, and critical infrastructures—transport, hospitals, industrial areas—face sudden disruption. In rural landscapes, the combination of

steep Apennine slopes and valley floors accelerates runoff, sending torrents of water toward low-lying towns and agricultural land. Equally problematic are multi-day rainfall events linked to slow-moving fronts or atmospheric rivers. These episodes saturate the landscape, raise groundwater levels, and strain river embankments along waterways such as the Reno, Savio, Secchia and Lamone. When 24-hour and 48-hour rainfall totals reach extremes, the region experiences cascading impacts: landslides in the hills and mountains, levee breaches in the plain, and widespread flooding that affects thousands of households and businesses. The severe floods of 2023 (May 2023, which resulted in damages estimated at 9 billion euros) made it unmistakably clear how intense rainfall has shifted from an episodic hazard to a structural driver of regional risk, challenging traditional monitoring systems and civil-protection practices. Emilia-Romagna has since accelerated efforts to modernise forecasting, strengthen hydraulic infrastructure, and integrate climate intelligence into land-use planning.

How does the CMCC Governance case study help ARPAE within the ASPECT project ?

The Governance Super User (ARPAE) contributed by co-developing an exploratory study on the use of climate predictions for strategic and operational water resources management, rather than by co-designing a fully operational prototype. ARPAE provided operational datasets, domain expertise, and continuous technical dialogue that helped frame the analysis around realistic governance needs and decision contexts. The study was explicitly designed to assess whether ARPAE's existing portfolio of climate services could be extended or enhanced based on the findings. Through this collaboration, ARPAE helped shape the delivery by ensuring methodological relevance, policy coherence, and alignment with existing institutional workflows, while ASPECT focused on experimentation, integration of multi-timescale climate predictions, and capacity building rather than service deployment. In this view, the co-production process has aimed to enhance the usability of climate information of Emilia-Romagna regional users with more niche climate data and technical modelling procedures. This continues to be co-developed thanks to the continuous engagement with the Governance Super User where technical experts constantly work to deliver refined and adaptive outputs to better match regional decision needs, spatial scales and communication preferences suggested by ARPAE. In summary, outputs have been discussed through a continuous learning process with the Super User, where relevant indicators, visualisations and modelling techniques have been agreed in order to improve the interpretation of the climate information for better regional decision action.

3.5.2. Delivery of Climate Information in the Governance Case Study

The technical dimensions underpinning the Governance case study will be focused particularly on three components, which are closely aligned with adaptation priorities identified for the Emilia-Romagna Region (each component will be extensively described in D4.3 - Delivery of co-developed case studies to meet the needs of superusers, however some info can also be found in the Section 7.3.1). These are:

#1 - High-resolution convective-permitting climate modelling (led by SMHI and University of Zagreb);

#2 - Statistical downscaling of dynamic-model predictions to regional planning scales (led by CMCC Bologna);

#3 - Application of climate projections in hydrological models (led by CMCC Venice).

The next section will go into the specific details about formats and delivery procedures of the three different components, explaining the rationale behind.

#1 High-resolution convective-permitting climate modelling (led by SMHI and University of Zagreb)

SMHI and University of Zagreb are currently collaborating with CMCC on the first component. In Governance case study, high-resolution modelling is essential because the region has chosen to focus on extreme convective rainfall and the kind of sudden, intense precipitation that recently caused severe impacts in its low-lying former floodplain areas. These events cannot be adequately captured with coarse climate models; they require detailed simulations that can resolve local atmospheric dynamics.

For the SMHI and Uni Zagreb part, the EBD–CPM approach² supports Super User by providing high-resolution, event-focused climate information that is directly relevant for risk assessment, emergency planning, and impact modelling. The improved representation of intensity, duration, and spatial patterns of rainfall and heat extremes offers credible inputs for hydrological and sectoral applications. To facilitate uptake, SMHI and Uni Zagreb will provide a synthesized report summarizing the scientific findings, together with standardized NetCDF datasets containing key variables from the downscaled extreme events and comprehensive documentation. All datasets and documentation will be made available through the ECMWF FTP server, while a dedicated webpage on the project website³ will host accessible descriptions of the methodology and guidance for users. The documentation will describe the modelling workflow, underlying assumptions, and main sources of uncertainty, enabling technically oriented users to understand, reproduce, and, where appropriate, adapt the framework to additional events or regions. Also, a peer-reviewed scientific publication will be prepared to provide a permanent reference for the methodology. This scalable and transparent delivery approach ensures that potential users can readily access and apply high-resolution, process-based climate information tailored to extreme events.

More specifically the data products will consist of

- A set of 50-100 extreme precipitation events from recent and future climate centered around SSP3-7.3 climate projections for 2030.
- A set of several tens of heat wave events from recent and future climate centered around SSP3-7.3 climate projections for 2030.

Those products have been chosen in discussions with stakeholders of the ASPECT Governance use case, who have identified those extremes as most relevant for climate adaptation. Real world examples for both types of extremes have occurred in the recent past and demonstrated severe impact. The data sets above are considered a service to high end users capable of performing their own statistical analyses. That is the case for the main stakeholder ARPAE.

Delivery Mode

² For technical details, please see Annex related to the Governance Case Study starting on page 77

³ <https://www.aspect-project.eu/dataset/>

Basically, the two sets of data will be made available via data server with access to users of the Governance case study. Those are advanced users with technical and scientific understanding to download, understand and process the data. Understanding of the data will be supported by documentation and subsequent scientific publication as outlined above.

The climate information will be made available

- Through the **ECMWF FTP server** (for accessing datasets such as NetCDF files).
- Through a **dedicated webpage** on the project site (for descriptive materials, documentation, and guidance).

Delivery Format

Data will be delivered in an established technical format including specific standards for variable names and standard ways to specify physical units. This data format is identical to the one used for scientific coordinated climate model intercomparison projects such as CMIP and CORDEX, both providing data which is processed for IPCC reports and for literally thousands of academic studies.

- **Standardized NetCDF/CF compliant datasets** following the CMOR metadata standard containing the high-resolution climate variables.
- A **synthesized scientific report** summarizing the modelling results.
- **Comprehensive documentation** detailing methodology, assumptions, workflow, and quantification of uncertainties.
- A **peer-reviewed publication** providing a permanent scientific reference.

The standard technical data format with a number of advantages (well documented standards, software availability, community of users, ...) was suggested to users and was fully accepted, due to the technical and scientific expertise of the users.

Delivery Visualisation

Any of the figures below have been demonstrated, commented on and in cases eventually amended by the stakeholders in the Governance case study in repeated group meetings and in individual exchanges.

Thresholds for the definition of extreme events were given by stakeholders including the use of maps that illustrate the spatial distribution and intensity of extreme events, helping practitioners immediately see where impacts concentrate. It also involves producing intensity–duration–frequency plots, which translate raw modelling outputs into decision-relevant metrics for planners and governance users. Visual summaries of rainfall or heat extremes provide a rapid overview of event characteristics, making it easier to compare scenarios or identify trends.

Altogether, these visual products serve as essential tools for interpreting high-resolution climate data, ensuring that both expert and non-expert users can navigate, evaluate, and apply the information effectively. Some examples of this visualisation could be found also in the CMCC Governance Case survey as well (please refer to Section 7.3.2):

Figure 17. Visualization example of ensemble average of daily precipitation for an extreme event 8 Oct 1996, in 12 km resolution.

An example of visualisation in this component could be a Figure 17 above, which shows the average rainfall amount (ensemble mean). The average of all ensemble members, called the ensemble mean, represents the most likely or expected rainfall amount for that event. It shows the general rainfall pattern that is common across all simulations, not a probability. In the meantime, by comparing the spread of members, scientists can also estimate the probability of rainfall exceeding a certain threshold (for example, 60 mm/day) at each location. For each figure a brief description of the variable is also provided. Another example could be the Figures 18 below, which show the probability that rainfall exceeded 60 and 100 mm/day, respectively.

Figure 18: Visualization example of probability of rainfall exceeding 60 mm/day and 100 mm/day, based on ensemble downscaling of an extreme event 8 Oct 1996.

Based on the ensemble outputs, the figures show the probability of rainfall exceeding 60 mm/day and 100 mm/day.

Another visualisation tool is shown in Figure 19, which compares how often heavy rainfall events of different intensities are expected to occur for two time periods: around 2000 (blue) and 2030 (red).

Figure 19. Visualization example of rainfall return period from 12 km downscaling of qualified extreme events based on a GCM ensemble of 50 members +/- 1 year around 2030

Each dot represents an observed extreme rainfall event, while the curved lines show the estimated rainfall amount expected for a given return period — that is, how many years on average between events of that intensity. The shaded areas represent the 95% confidence interval, meaning scientists are 95% confident that the true rainfall amount for each return period lies within that shaded range. A wider shaded area indicates greater uncertainty in the estimate, while a narrower shaded area means the prediction is more certain.

Another visualisation example provided by SMHI and University of Zagreb in Figure 20.

Figure 20. Visualization example of mean nighttime temperature in recent and future climate.

The two maps show the nighttime air temperature during two tropical night events for two different periods: around the year 2000 (left) and around 2030 (right).

Figure 21 instead illustrates the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect in the Bologna region, showing how nighttime temperature changes from the city center to the surrounding areas up to 30 km away. The shaded areas in the right graph show the range of variability among different locations or simulations. Warmer colors in the maps indicate higher nighttime temperatures, and a larger temperature difference near the city center means a stronger UHI effect.

The data products will include a representative number of heat wave events which will be visualized by figures such as the ones provided here.

Figure 21. Visualization example for urban heat island effect for Bologna, for recent and future climate.

Further visualization will be provided regarding extreme precipitation events, in the form of maps and also as statistically integrated views over ca 50 events for recent and future climate. The latter visualizations will allow for interpretation of future development of precipitation extremes, based on the prototype development in ASPECT.

The delivery strategy is designed to support advanced technical users, such as Super User (e.g. ARPAE), by providing full-resolution datasets and complete methodological transparency. At the same time, it ensures reproducibility and scalability, allowing other regions or researchers to adapt the approach and enabling future extensions using updated global climate model data. Accessibility is guaranteed through the provision of both high-level summaries and detailed technical documentation, catering to users with different levels of expertise. Clear and intuitive visualisations are included to enhance trust and usability, helping users interpret complex modelling outputs. Finally, the approach aligns with co-design principles by enabling stakeholders to engage with the information at varying levels of technical capacity.

#2 Statistical downscaling of dynamic-model predictions to regional planning scales (led by CMCC Bologna)

CMCC Bologna leads the second component developing the statistical downscaling method for the region. Large-scale climate projections must be translated into spatial and temporal resolutions that are meaningful for urban planning, agricultural management, and infrastructure protection. Emilia-Romagna's urban centres—such as Bologna and Parma—along with the communities located in vulnerable floodplain zones, require this level of detail to design credible adaptation strategies. For this work, the CMCC group in Bologna plans to issue predictions up to 10 years into the future by combining plots (e.g. spatial maps of predicted variables in Emilia-Romagna) and explanatory text highlighting the key takeaway points. Predictions will always be accompanied by statements about their ability to predict past states of the climate as measured in hindcast sets.

The climate information produced will likely be delivered to the user in the form of a **scientific document (fact-sheet)**. The document will begin with a brief summary listing the target variables considered, the selected forecast horizon, and other essential information. The expected changes for the coming years (compared to recent decades) will be presented as **spatial maps of predicted anomaly fields** or **probabilities of categorical events**. The plots will be complemented by concise statements summarising the key points, and by a short discussion of the expected prediction skill based on the performance of the method over a set of retrospective predictions. The information will be organised in sections, each section corresponding to a specific choice of target variable/forecast period. The exact nature of the plots shown and metrics used to evaluate hindcast skill will depend on specific user requirements, and be subject to the constraints posed by scientific feasibility.

Rationale

ARPAE is a research-oriented public agency with expertise in producing and elaborating complex climate information. ARPAE assists and cooperates with local agencies and consortia whose operations are impacted by weather and climate phenomena. In order to suit a spectrum of technical requirements determined by the local users' specific needs,

ARPAE would benefit from receiving climate information endowed with a high level of scientific detail from this activity and in directions that ARPAE itself has not previously explored. Our choices, presented below, cater for this necessity: this delivery approach supports evidence-based decision-making, accommodates different governance capacities and provides a replicable framework for future assessments.

Delivery mode

The climate information produced by the CMCC group in Bologna will be delivered to the end-user primarily in the form of a scientific document (fact-sheet) combining plots and explanatory text (more details in section “Delivery format” below). This choice is tailored to the specific needs expressed by ARPAE during multi-lateral meetings between ASPECT and ARPAE representatives. The report may be complemented by peer-reviewed scientific publications providing comprehensive detail on input data, methodologies, and procedures.

Delivery format

The planned structure of the scientific report to be delivered to ARPAE is designed to convey ASPECT climate information that is complementary to what ARPAE itself produces and to accommodate ARPAE’s technical requirements, as illustrated below.

The document will begin with a brief summary listing the target variables considered, the selected forecast horizons, and all other information essential to understand the accompanying material. The target variables have been identified based on ARPAE’s own “[Rapporto Idro-Meteo-Clima Emilia-Romagna](#)” (a yearly dissemination report spanning a range of climate-related subjects, where technical definitions for a number of variables of interest are given), and following liaison with ARPAE’s representatives. The predictions’ horizon (decadal) has been selected to expand and complement ARPAE’s existing prediction portfolio (which currently includes seasonal —but not decadal— predictions.)

The information will be organised in sections, each section corresponding to a specific choice of target variable/forecast period. The expected changes for the coming years (compared to recent decades) will be presented as spatial maps of predicted anomaly fields. Following ARPAE’s suggestion, probabilities of categorical events (above/below average) will also be displayed, accompanied by legends and/or colorbars as appropriate for interpretability.

The plots will be complemented by concise statements summarising the key points, and by a short discussion of the expected prediction skill based on the performance of the method over a set of retrospective predictions (where common skill metrics will be used for the evaluations. See an example in section “Delivery visualisation” below). Access to information on hindcast skill was identified as a key element by the end-user in the course of multi-lateral meetings.

Delivery visualisation

In adherence to the end-user’s preference on the level of technical detail, climate information will be presented visually following state-of-the-art scientific practice. Specifically, visual items will include:

- **Maps of multi-year averaged anomalies**, showing how future conditions differ from a reference climate.
- **Probability charts or categorical maps**, illustrating chances of wetter/drier or hotter/cooler conditions over the forecast window.
- **Skill maps**, illustrating the performance of the method over retrospective predictions according to a range of skill metrics.

An example of a skill map is shown in Figure 22, where skill is measured by the Pearson correlation coefficient. Graphics of this kind will illustrate where the prediction performs well, where it shows little association with reality, and where results are statistically significant. By using colour scales and spatial grids, users can quickly grasp the strengths and limitations of the predictive method across Emilia-Romagna. This visual approach makes an inherently technical concept—referring to forecast skill—accessible and directly interpretable for practitioners and decision-makers.

Figure 22. Pearson correlation coefficient between observed and retrospectively predicted winter precipitation over Emilia-Romagna averaged over forecast years 1–10. Dots mark grid points where the coefficient is statistically significant at the 95% confidence level according to a one-sided t-test.

Figure 23 illustrates what a typical decadal prediction will look like within this activity. It shows a retrospective forecast of anomalous winter (DJF) mean precipitation over Emilia-Romagna averaged over forecast years 1–10 for initialisation year 2000. Green areas indicate wetter-than-normal conditions, while brown areas signal drier conditions. Every real-time prediction will be accompanied by a corresponding skill assessment, ensuring that users can judge where and to what extent the predicted anomalies are trustworthy, based on past hindcast performance.

Figure 23. Retrospectively-predicted anomalous winter (DJF) mean precipitation over Emilia-Romagna averaged over forecast years 1–10 for initialisation year 2000. The anomaly is computed with respect to the 1991–2010 period.

#3 Application of climate projections in hydrological models (led by CMCC Venice)

This component⁴, led by CMCC Venice, focuses on the application of climate projections within hydrological modelling frameworks to address key challenges related to water availability and river dynamics in Northern Italy. The work targets the Po River Basin District (PRBD), the largest river basin in Italy, with particular emphasis on the Secchia and Reno river basins. The PRBD spans six regions, including Emilia-Romagna, Veneto, and the Autonomous Province of Trento, all of which are involved in the Mission Adaptation. The district hosts a highly developed agricultural sector, significant industrial activities, and major urban centres such as Milan and Bologna, making it especially vulnerable to climate-driven hydrological extremes.

The core hydrological engine used in this workflow is GEOFRAME, a semi-distributed, process-based model developed by the University of Trento. For benchmarking and comparison purposes, additional modelling approaches were employed, including the HYPE hydrological model and a suite of machine learning (ML) and Graph Neural Network (GNN) models. This multi-model strategy allows both physically based and data-driven perspectives on streamflow simulation and climate impact assessment.

For the Secchia River Basin, the analysis focuses on the upper catchment upstream of the Lugo gauge station, an area minimally influenced by anthropogenic regulation. This setting enables a near-natural assessment of hydrological processes such as runoff generation, evapotranspiration, infiltration, and groundwater recharge. GEOFRAME was calibrated for the period 2003–2017 and validated for 2018–2023, achieving satisfactory Kling-Gupta Efficiency values. In parallel, multiple ML models were tested, with GNNs showing superior performance in streamflow prediction compared to traditional ML techniques and, in some

⁴ For technical details, please see the Annex section 8.3

metrics, outperforming GEOFRAME. Despite this, GEOFRAME remains central due to its ability to explicitly represent the full water balance and internal hydrological states.

For the Reno River Basin, a semi-distributed HYPE model was applied to three sub-basins (Pracchia, Vergato, and Casalecchio), using high-resolution gridded meteorological inputs (ERG5 dataset). The model was calibrated over 2001–2018 and validated over 2019–2022. As in the Secchia case, traditional ML models and GNNs were tested to assess the added value of explicitly representing spatial connectivity in hydrological simulations.

Delivery Mode

The delivery mode is centred on capacity building rather than the provision of a fully operational climate service. The objective is to strengthen the ability of regional administrations and public authorities to incorporate climate information into anticipatory and adaptive water management strategies. This is achieved through structured interactions, workshops, and discussion sessions, where stakeholders are actively engaged in understanding climate projections, hydrological modelling outputs, and associated uncertainties.

At this stage, the focus is on co-learning and governance support rather than automated service delivery. However, a potential operational pipeline is being explored within the CLIMAAX framework, which could enable future integration into a more formalised climate service.

Delivery Format

The main delivery consists of a synthesised scientific report that documents the full workflow, including methodology, event selection, assumptions, model configurations, and key findings. The report provides transparent documentation of uncertainties and offers guidance on how to interpret and responsibly use the results in decision-making contexts. In addition to the report, all datasets, model outputs, and supporting documentation are made openly accessible through an online archive, ensuring reproducibility, traceability, and ease of uptake by technical users and institutions.

Delivery Visualisation

Visualisation plays a key role in facilitating understanding among non-technical and semi-technical users. The delivery includes exploratory data analysis outputs that compare observed, simulated, and projected river discharge under different scenarios. These visual products focus on average conditions as well as specific hydrological events, highlighting changes in intensity, duration, and spatial patterns. Visualisations may integrate results from both process-based models and ML approaches, including improved calibration outputs for GEOFRAME, to illustrate strengths, limitations, and complementarities across modelling techniques. Summary figures and intuitive graphics are designed to support interpretation and discussion during workshops and capacity-building activities.

The Super User (ARPAE) contributed to shaping how the hydrological modelling results were delivered by co-developing an exploratory application of climate predictions for water-resources management, rather than by directly defining model variables, visual outputs, or exceedance thresholds. ARPAE supported the work by providing hydrological and meteorological datasets for model calibration, as well as domain knowledge and ongoing

technical dialogue that helped situate the modelling results within realistic governance and water-management contexts. This interaction ensured that the presentation and interpretation of hydrological outputs were consistent with existing institutional practices and decision-support workflows. Within this framework, ASPECT focused on methodological experimentation, integration of climate predictions into hydrological modelling, and capacity building, rather than on the development of an operational hydrological service.

Overall, the chosen delivery approach aims to ensure that the governance-focused case study provides transparent, reproducible, and user-friendly climate information. By prioritising interaction, explanation, and visual clarity, the component supports the gradual familiarisation of public administrations with climate forecasts and hydrological projections. This strategy is intended to help governance structures overcome institutional and technical barriers, enabling decision-makers to move beyond reactive responses and towards robust, anticipatory water management under climate change. The combination of open data, clear documentation, and participatory engagement is essential to building trust in climate information and fostering its effective use in policy and planning processes.

4. How have these prototypes been perceived by Super Users and other potential users?

Co-production with sector experts or end-users is a key part of the ASPECT approach to the case studies to ensure that seamless climate science and service development provides information that is useful and usable within the decision-making context. An important question is whether this co-produced knowledge is also useful for a broader pool of potential users in the sector. Task 5.5 (led by Work Package 5) is designing surveys to examine the extent to which co-produced climate information from the ASPECT project is also useful and usable for meeting the decision needs of other similar potential users, following the typology of climate information use proposed by [Jagannathan et al. \(2023\)](#). Although findings will be explored in more detail in future ASPECT deliverables, below we include some initial results from these surveys (from very limited numbers of respondents so far), together with other feedback from Super Users or other users through engagement in other forums.

4.1. Agriculture case study

The wine survey was first disseminated on 19 November 2025 to wine companies and trade bodies in different countries so few responses have been received so far. This survey is only based on the first part of the bulletin which provides relevant climate information for the spring frost protection. Initial perspectives gathered from two survey respondents provided positive assessments of the climate information prototype co-developed with our Super User Codorníu in terms of its format, understandability, and perceived benefits both for themselves and for their organisations. They agreed that such a prototype could help their organisations better understand the conditions that cause management challenges, input data for impact modelling activities, and inform the development of climate change plans. They also saw value in the prototype's potential to guide operational or management adjustments, as well as decisions related to retrofitting existing infrastructure or undertaking new infrastructure projects.

During the Climateurope2 (CE2) Festival held in Belgrade, Serbia, in autumn 2025, ASPECT scientists hosted a World Café session titled “Exploring the potential to scale up co-produced climate information in the wine sector” with three participants representing environmental consulting, the EU research policy directorate, and an agri-tech company. Participants agreed that such seasonal and decadal climate information would be useful for certain niche wine producers or large-scale vineyards. Participants however speculated that wine producers that relied on traditional knowledge and experience when making decisions, may not be early adopters of new climate information services. Additionally, as some climate impacts such as frost damage, can be insured or accepted as a routine budgeted loss, small vineyards may not appreciate the benefit of purchasing such climate information services.

Both respondents to the questionnaire and participants in the World Café provided suggestions for future improvements to the prototype. They noted that some explanations and charts related to frost days could be simplified. They also expressed a desire for the spatial resolution to be further downscaled to match their preferred geographic scale, as microclimatic variability can be decisive and conditions often vary within just a few meters. In addition, they showed interest in incorporating other climate parameters and indicators, such as heatwave days, drought conditions, precipitation, evapotranspiration, wind, and growing-season average temperature.

4.2. Humanitarian case study

The prototype climate bulletin originally developed for the Agriculture case study has been presented to Save the Children International as an example of the format and type of information envisaged for the Humanitarian case study. The Super User expressed strong interest and appreciation for the approach and design, recognising its value in summarising complex climate information in an actionable and easy-to-understand way.

Currently, the content and structure of the SCI-specific bulletin are being co-developed with the Super User. SCI is reviewing the prototype and has been invited to provide feedback on the preferred indicators, temporal scales, and presentation formats, ensuring that the final version meets their anticipatory action and nutrition planning needs.

This iterative exchange is a central element of the co-design process, ensuring alignment between scientific outputs and the operational realities of humanitarian decision-making. Early feedback suggests that the bulletin format is well suited for SCI’s workflows, although further customisation may be needed to emphasise nutrition-relevant variables (such as drought severity, rainfall anomalies, and temperature variations).

In parallel, the interactive Shiny App has been demonstrated to SCI and other potential users. It was perceived as a valuable tool for exploring forecast data and assessing model performance, particularly by technically trained staff. However, non-technical users expressed a preference for the more summarised and narrative format of the bulletin (consistent with the feedback received by the Super User in the Agriculture case study). This reinforces the decision to prioritise the bulletin as the main communication product, complemented by potential training sessions and forecast briefings to strengthen user capacity in interpreting and applying the information.

4.3. Finance (pensions) case study

Perceptions of the website aimed at pension trustees

A survey (created by the University of Leeds) was first shared in the summer of 2025 and it is currently ongoing. The following results should be interpreted with caution, since they only comprise views from 4 respondents. The survey is targeting individuals working in the pension sector and whose investments are sensitive to weather/ climate impacts. At the time of writing this deliverable, four respondents had completed the questionnaire. More information about the survey and results is available in Annex 8.4.1. Briefly we share some key findings. With respect to understandability, all 4 respondents indicated that the balance between text and images in the storyboard was appropriate. However, they did not find the prototype easy to understand. The prototype was perceived positively in terms of trustworthiness, accuracy, usability, and format suitability.

Perceptions of training delivered in financial sector hackathon

In the feedback forms from the hackathon, we received several responses around this training, with 4 out of 9 respondents positively agreeing that this training helped them feel more confident in applying decadal predictions. More information is available in Annex 8.4.2.

4.4. Emergency response case study

In-person training

The British Red Cross UK Operations Lead - Crisis and Emergency Response, noted the clear benefits of co-production in the planning of in-person training at the National Emergency Response Group in March 2025: “the opportunity for (the Met Office trainers) to integrate their support with (the) British Red Cross Insight Team at an early stage in the training design wielded dividends in terms of the **quality** and **relevance** of the training.” They also praised “the willingness to **tailor** sessions to support the development of analysis techniques among our operational managers”.

After the in-person event, direct feedback from 14 responders around the in-person training reflected a substantial increase in confidence from the in-person training. Confidence before the session on interpreting seasonal forecasts was rated as 2.4 out of 5 on average, and confidence after the session was rated as 4.3 out of 5 on average, representing an increase of 1.9 on average. Confidence in using the Local Authority Climate Service before the session was rated as 1.2 out of 5 on average, and confidence after the session was rated as 3.9 out of 5 on average, representing an increase of 2.7 on average. The sessions were found to be enjoyable, with a rating of 4.4 out of 5 on average. Please see Annex 8.4.3. for more information.

Further feedback was later received from the British Red Cross UK Operations Lead - Crisis and Emergency Response, who provided additional verbal feedback to ASPECT in a meeting in June 2025. They elaborated on the subsequent use of the Local Authority Climate

Service tool after the training by different teams in the British Red Cross with a particular example given - the use of Local Authority Climate Service for prioritisation of support across London boroughs.

Website

We have been working together to develop the content for the website together with the British Red Cross, principally the Climate Adaptation and Resilience Manager. The content of the website has been amended many times as an iterative co-production process with the British Red Cross has continued. Below is a quote provided by the Climate Adaptation and Resilience Manager about the process and prototype product we have co-designed.

"Working with the Met Office to co-develop the website under the ASPECT project has been a highly constructive and collaborative process. It marks an important milestone in embedding climate-informed thinking into British Red Cross emergency response operations. I believe the ASPECT website will be a valuable tool for our emergency responders, helping them build the awareness and confidence to factor climate-informed thinking into their decision-making".

Summer Wyatt-Buchan **Climate Adaptation and Resilience Manager, British Red Cross**

We are now planning to assess the utility and value of the website tool with emergency responders and operational managers, reflecting different personas in the British Red Cross. At the time of writing, we are designing a strategy to assess the tool with different emergency responders from across the organisation. This process will likely provide additional insights into the potential use or improvements that can be made to the tool.

4.5. Governance case study

Many communities face increasing climate risks but lack adequate financial resources, technical expertise and institutional capacity to identify, assess and manage them effectively. Insufficient data, limited access to planning tools and shortages of qualified professionals hinder adaptation planning as well. For this reason, the prototype survey of the Governance case study will be launched within the EU-funded [CLIMAAX Community of Practice \(COP\)](#), a key CMCC partner project.

The main objective of CLIMAAX is to support European regions, communities and local/regional authorities in identifying, assessing and managing climate-related risks — in particular through the development of multi-hazard assessments (including floods, droughts, heatwaves, extreme events, environmental vulnerability, and more)⁵.

Therefore, CLIMAAX aims to strengthen local and regional capacities by helping communities better understand the climate risks they face and evaluate past progress in risk assessment. Specifically, the [CLIMAAX](#) project contributes to this effort by:

- Connect regions and practitioners working on Climate Risk Assessments (CRA).

⁵ https://www.cimafoundation.org/en/project/climaax/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

- Foster co-design, knowledge exchange, and mutual learning.
- Bridge the gap between risk assessment and adaptation planning.

The launch of the Governance survey in the CLIMAAX COP has then both strategic aim and rationale behind. First of all, it represents a niche governance users pool and community, since the majority of the Community of Practices are local and regional authorities (> 300 members). In this context, the survey developed by the CMCC Governance case study within ASPECT is well positioned and aligned with CLIMAAX needs and creates a favorable environment for the implementation of Governance survey.

During the CLIMAAX COP, we aim to exploit the session as a live testbed where regional and local authorities can interact with the Governance case study survey, allowing them to have immediate hands-on experience. In addition to that, it could serve as pilot testers or early adopters of ASPECT Governance Case tools. The main idea is then to distribute the survey on the 11th December 2025, i.e the next CLIMAAX COP. The desired goal is to have some initial feedback about the scalability of this prototype, as well as understand the variability in governance adaptation capacity. This is because while technically advanced actors such as ARPAE operate in environments rich in research infrastructures, modelling expertise and established protocols, many regional and local authorities do not share these advantages. They often work with limited staff, minimal technical training and fragmented information. By comparing these contrasting situations, we aim to understand what types of support—whether methodological, organisational or technological—are necessary to bridge the gap between high-capacity and low-capacity users.

A second critical dimension could be related to the barriers that prevent climate data and modelling outputs from informing real policy decisions. Indeed, even when data exists, it may be scattered across institutions, delivered in overly technical formats or lack clear guidance on interpretation.

Lastly, another key goal we intend to understand is how the CLIMAAX community grasps the CMCC Governance case study survey delivered. Specifically, we would like to test if the survey feels intuitive, adequately tailored to diverse professional backgrounds, and aligned with the realities of decision-making. Our aim is not merely to collect information, but to ensure the survey becomes a strategic tool that empowers regional and local authorities by reflecting their actual needs and challenges in the long-run. This would lead us to identify opportunities to improve the alignment between climate risk assessment and adaptation planning, avoiding misalignments between scientific outputs and policy priorities.

To summarise, the launch of CMCC Governance Case survey in the CLIMAAX COP aims to:

- 1) Replicability across regions: assess whether the survey structure and questions can be applied to governance bodies with very different levels of technical capacity, institutional maturity and access to climate information.
- 2) Flexibility of formats: test if the survey accommodates both highly technical users (e.g., ARPAE) and low-capacity authorities (e.g., small municipalities) without losing relevance or clarity.
- 3) Transferability of insights: evaluate whether the information collected can support the development of governance tools usable by a broad spectrum of European regions beyond Emilia-Romagna.
- 4) Adaptability to diverse governance systems: determine if the survey can be customised for different administrative structures, legal frameworks and climate-risk

governance arrangements.

The survey's prototype of the Governance case study is developed and finalised, allowing governance end-users to test the usability, clarity, and relevance of the climate information produced. For transparency and documentation purposes, the current version of the survey slide deck (provided using a Powerpoint file type) is shared in Annex 8.3.2.

5. Discussion looking at synergies and differences across the different case studies

5.1. Key Lessons Learnt

5.1.1. Decision-relevance to drive change

There is ongoing debate about the extent to which climate services influence decision-making. Traditionally, these services have focused on improving data provision, which is widely valued and used by technical users across sectors. However, tracking how such data informs decisions is inherently difficult, especially when data is publicly funded and freely accessible. Some examples of use are not published due to confidentiality or lack of incentives for disclosure. Moreover, climate-informed decision-making is ideally iterative and ongoing, with climate information forming only one component. This complexity further limits efforts to quantify direct influence.

Recent research (e.g., [Findlater et al. 2021](#), [Reveco-Umaña 2023](#)) highlights that influencing decision making processes requires climate services to go beyond the data provision and engage with decision making processes, user demands, and to understand users' social context. In line with this, ASPECT has explored the decision-making environment of its Super Users during co-production. The prototypes integrate social and institutional contexts into both service design and the development of quantitative methods, ensuring that they are useful and usable for supporting decision making.

This user-centred approach recognises that climate services must be accessible, interpretable, and relevant to diverse users within organisations, spanning both technical and non-technical roles. By accounting for differing levels of expertise and decision authority, climate services can better support climate-informed actions and help embed climate considerations across organisations and sectors.

5.1.2. The importance of stepping back to step forward to support climate-informed thinking

When considering how to help embed climate-informed thinking across an organisation, we recognise that many potential users of the prototype material will not be familiar with climate information. Although ASPECT operates in a complex scientific space across predictions to projections, from a climate services perspective, we know we need to step back to ensure that information is provided at a suitable level, and to co-produce outputs that are appropriate and useful to support decision making.

We identified the need to build easy to use tools that provide necessary knowledge at a sustainable pace to support relevant decision-making, whilst building capacity around the

interpretation of seamless climate information. When relevant technical information around new data or methods are published, it can be directly linked or layered within a website tool (for example) so that it is findable for those who need it. Ideally, the main messages can also be provided in a more accessible format, with for example, key information provided in a blog or short briefing. From a climate service and relationship management perspective it is also important to not stress user relationships by pushing an inappropriate pace or interaction, as this risks future engagement.

5.1.3. Training as a critical element of a climate service

Training is recognised as a key component of effective climate services, supporting users in understanding and applying climate information. Within ASPECT, training has been integrated into service delivery through both interactive sessions and the development of accessible online materials, with prototype websites also serving as training resources. Across sectors, training is essential for enabling Super Users to interpret climate information at critical decision points and for building long-term capacity. By embedding training within climate service products, ASPECT aims to support sustained use and internal ownership of climate-informed decision-making.

5.1.4. The benefits of a broad network within an organisation for relationship continuity

The co-development of the climate service prototypes can be affected by organisational and staff changes within the end user organisation. This could lead to periods without a clear focal point for engagement which can also introduce delays, highlighting the need for flexible engagement strategies when working with complex institutions. Building relationships across different roles and levels within an organisation increases resilience to personnel changes and supports sustained co-production for a long research project. Within a span of 3-4 years, the chance of key staff moving on, or organisational changes, are reasonably high, and therefore, if possible, having previously established relationships that can help bridge gaps in key staff engagement is hugely valuable. This is particularly important where the partnership is an ‘in-kind’ research relationship with no financial incentives.

5.1.5. The challenges of resolution

Most user-oriented climate studies or applications use the highest available resolution observations or climate projection data in line with user requests for local-scale resolution. This now sets the expectation of users to access high resolution (~1 km) data and information, with user desire for even finer resolutions (for example, valley or neighbourhood level). This is a particular issue when considering prediction data as in its raw form it is a resolution of around 60 km over Europe. The nature of climate variability means that prediction data are not necessarily skilful at fine resolution for many hazards, especially consistently across a wide range of locations (e.g. country or continental areas). This is a particular challenge for applications where we are attempting to support users who are simultaneously interested in many locations.

At the same time, limitations in model resolution and process representation mean that some risks, particularly related to extreme rainfall ([Chen et al. 2021](#), [Kendon et al. 2021](#)) or temperature ([Kay et al. 2025](#)), may be underestimated in regional and global scale climate modelling products. Communicating these limitations transparently is an important part of user engagement, enabling informed interactions with climate service providers. Ongoing

methodological developments devoted to increasing the spatial resolution of the climate information, including the combination of different modelling systems (e.g. combination of predictions with convection permitting models, [Kent et al. 2022](#)), machine-learning emulators ([Kendon et al. 2025](#)), and approaches that link large-scale forecasts with historical observations ([Stringer et al. 2020](#)), offer promising pathways to enhance the spatial detail and usability of predictive climate information. While many of these techniques are still under development, they highlight future opportunities for delivering more locally relevant and decision-relevant climate services.

5.1.6. Co-production among public institutions and climate scientists

Previous research has already shown that both scientific advances and institutional processes must adapt together, ensuring that advanced tools (e.g., convective-permitting simulations, regional downscaling, and hydrological projections), communication, and procedures are compatible with decision making processes ([Lynch & Brunner 2010](#), [Bharwani et al. 2024](#)). Multi-level governance studies further stress the need for continuous learning loops across regional and local authorities to embed climate knowledge into long-term adaptation processes ([González-Iwanciw et al., 2020](#)).

Regional authorities and local administration users require climate information that is up-to-date, reliable, policy-relevant, and aligned with administrative decision cycles. Governance users often operate within sector-specific contexts and consequently demand user relevant metrics that are not commonly used in the research context and require bespoke analysis. Successful climate adaptation depends not only on technical innovation but also on the alignment of climate science with governance capacity and decision needs, achieved through structured co-production, integration into institutional processes, and ongoing and iterative collaboration.

5.1.7. Lack of continuity after the project completion

The co-development of the case studies is constrained to the four years of the project, or less than three years in the case of the second cohort of Super Users. The lack of continuity once the project funding period ends is a limitation for sustained engagement with the users. While the project supports the co-development of the climate service prototypes, there are no dedicated resources to ensure long-term maintenance, updates, or operational delivery. This discontinuity affected user expectations and reduced the potential impact of the prototypes as Super Users are not guaranteed to be able to use them in future decision-making. Hence, to maximise the long term impact of the project, it is critical to plan exploitation and legacy activities, which ideally may include the operationalisation of some of the ASPECT climate service prototypes.

5.2. Recommendations for data delivery to users

Building on key lessons learnt from the co-exploration and co-production processes described in the previous section, as well as challenges faced as climate service practitioners in developing these prototypes, this section translates those insights into a set of practical recommendations for data delivery to users. These recommendations aim to support the effective uptake of climate information by ensuring that data are delivered in a way that is accessible, interpretable, and aligned with user needs and decision-making contexts.

5.2.1. Data delivery for technical users

Based on our experiences as internal users of ASPECT data, and our institutional collective knowledge of a range of users, we recommend the supplying of example code or notebooks to support technical users in getting started with the data processing and analysis of prediction data, given the complexities inherent in its meaningful use alongside other sources of climate information in climate services.

Alongside providing findable data, we also recommend the creation of frequently asked questions to help support people starting to use prediction information in a meaningful way. For example, questions and answers that might be provided by prediction experts include the following topics:

- Key strengths and limitations of the multi-annual and multi-decadal simulations relative to existing prediction datasets.
- Common misunderstandings or pitfalls that users might wish to avoid when using the datasets.
- Where there is easily accessible information about skill.
- How might predictions be used to provide information about daily-timescale extremes of common interest to society, such as short duration heatwaves and heavy rainfall.
- Information around emissions forcings and aerosol forcing (including transparency around the potential limitations of outdated aerosol forcing for predictions).
- Information about bias adjustments that are recommended or might otherwise be made.
- Information about testing for signal-to-noise errors, and potentially information on how the mean signal from a prediction ensemble could potentially be ‘boosted’.
- How to best use the ensemble or the median/mean for different applications.
- Information about the multi-model mean compared to using models from different modelling systems, and best practice especially when models show different responses.
- Information about any available platforms or online plotting tools to help visualise and interact with any postprocessed data available.

5.2.2. Data delivery for non-technical users

Our Super User group reflects that many potential users of climate information do not have the time, skills, knowledge or experience to download large datasets and write code to analyse climate data. They also might not have sufficient resources to employ climate service providers to do this on their behalf. Tools which supply data and information through a website portal (e.g. the ASPECT-funded [ERA Explorer](#) and [Thermal Trace](#) applications, and the [Met Office Local Authority Climate Service Explorer](#)) are particularly in demand for users across low to intermediate technical levels, as they can also save a technically skilled user significant time if they provide the metrics required.

It will be useful for predictions and seamless data and skill assessments to be provided in similar user-focused and easy to access browser applications, which can then be accessed by end-users when they need them in flexible ways. However, given the size of prediction and seamless data we note that there are considerable challenges for any organisation to provide this data hosting service, and this has not been able to be achieved for prediction data yet within ASPECT under WP6 Application Development. Due to the size of the data there is significant cost of the service to host and storing large prediction data in an easily

accessible way for rapid access applications (like ERA Explorer), as well as significant service development including the resource effort required to process potential user metrics of interest in a consistent way. There are also scientific challenges around providing skilful information at a local level over Europe. Therefore, substantial effort would also be required, including user testing, to consider how users can be appropriately supported in how/when this information is appropriate to use, to mitigate against the risk that prediction-based, or in future, seamless merged, climate information might be used inappropriately in decision making.

When relevant information about new data or methods are published, they can also be directly linked or layered within applications so that information is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR principles, [Wilkinson et al. 2016](#)) for those who need it. Ideally, the main messages can be provided in accessible, engaging formats, such as diagrams, infographics, plain language summaries, and/or key points as an entry point for the information. Press briefings, blogs and briefing notes are typical methods by which we expect that many users will access climate information for use in climate-informed decision making.

5.3. Summary

- Providing climate information to just one user within an organisation may not be sufficient for influencing decision-making, especially in the case of most of our Super Users who do not have extensive technical expertise in-house for analysing climate data. To better support decision-making across many sectors, climate data and information should be accessible and useful for both technical and non-technical profiles, as all these users contribute to decision-making processes.
- Supporting climate-informed thinking often requires stepping back to simplify, reassess, and co-produce information at an appropriate level.
- Training is essential for enabling users to correctly interpret and apply climate information, transforming a climate service from a set of products into a usable decision-support tool.
- During the co-production of a case study, it is essential to maintain a broad network within the organisation to ensure continuity of relationships and avoid delays.
- The potential impact of the climate service prototypes is constrained by the absence of resources after project completion to support their long-term maintenance and operation.
- Providing climate data to technical users is most effective when they include practical guidance, such as example code, blended code/training resources such as jupyter notebooks, and documentation which includes both technical and scientific guidance. This helps users understand dataset limitations, common pitfalls, and best practices for analysis, enabling meaningful and robust use of the data.
- The provision of climate data to non-technical users requires accessible tools to interact with these data, such as web portals or bulletins. Tailoring information to their needs supports informed decision-making while minimizing the risk of misinterpretation.

6. Conclusions

This deliverable presents the outcomes of the co-exploration process undertaken with ASPECT Super Users to identify effective approaches for delivering climate information. By adopting an agile and user-centric methodology, the project has been able to adapt to evolving scientific developments while ensuring that user needs remain central to the design of the climate service prototypes.

The co-exploration processes across the different case studies have shown that climate information must be accessible, interpretable, and relevant for both technical and non-technical profiles within organisations. Furthermore, the co-production of climate information should be carried out at an appropriate level, which often requires reducing the complexity of climate products. This simplification is fundamental to facilitate the uptake of climate information in specific decision-making processes. Another key component that emerges is the effective climate services training, as it enables users to correctly interpret uncertainties, limitations, and the appropriate application of climate information.

Overall, the findings of this deliverable identify a set of emerging good practices for the co-production and delivery of climate information and services that are both scientifically robust and decision-relevant.

These lessons will directly inform the continued development and refinement of climate data and service provision within the ASPECT project, contributing to the broader objective of delivering seamless, user-driven climate information that effectively supports adaptation-related decision-making. Nevertheless, while the climate service prototypes developed within ASPECT demonstrate clear potential to support decision-making across multiple sectors, their long-term impact may be constrained by the availability of resources beyond the project lifetime.

7. Annexes

7.1. Bulletin - Viticulture (Example version as at December 2025)

BULLETIN
Campaigns 2025-26

Seasonal & decadal
predictions
for
Viticulture

 Earth Sciences
Department

Barcelona Supercomputing
Centro Nacional de Supercomputación

DESDE 1951

www.aspect-project.eu

FROST PROTECTION SUMMARY

Lower than normal probability of spring frost in Catalunya

A below normal number of frost days is predicted in March-April 2025 in Catalunya. Decadal forecasts also show a lower than normal risk of spring frost in March-April 2026 in the province of Lleida.

There is a high probability of above normal growing degree days in March 2025, especially in the southern part of Catalunya, indicating an earlier growing of the plant. Forecasts do not show a clear signal for the probability of growing degree days in 2026.

WATER MANAGEMENT SUMMARY

Drier/wetter than normal growing season in Catalunya

A below normal number of frost days is predicted in March-April 2025 in Catalunya. Decadal forecasts also show a lower than normal risk of spring frost in March-April 2026 in the province of Lleida.

There is a high probability of above normal growing degree days in March 2025, especially in the southern part of Catalunya, indicating an earlier growing of the plant. Forecasts do not show a clear signal for the probability of growing degree days in 2026.

If you have queries or feedback, contact us:
 hello-aspect@bsc.es

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USER GUIDE

FROST PROTECTION INDICATORS

Frost days (FD)

Number of days with minimum temperature below 0°C between March 1st and April 30th

Growing Degree Days (GDD)

Accumulated sum of daily differences between daily mean temperature and 10°C (vegetative growth minimum temperature), excluding days with mean temperature above 30°C, between March 1st and April 30th

WATER MANAGEMENT INDICATORS

Growing season total precipitation

Total precipitation from April 1st to September 30th

Growing season average temperature

Average of daily average temperatures between April 1st and September 30th

Standardised Precipitation and Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI)

Index that assesses water availability for the plants by comparing the balance between precipitation and potential evapotranspiration during the growing season of the vineyard (April-September). SPEI6 is useful to predict agricultural drought

Growing Degree Days (GDD)

Accumulated sum of daily differences between daily mean temperature and 10°C (vegetative growth minimum temperature), excluding days with mean temperature above 30°C, between April 1st and September 30th

Heatwave

Count of days with at least 3 consecutive days when the daily maximum temperature exceeds 36°C between April 1st and September 30th

TIME SCALES

Seasonal predictions

Probabilistic forecasts of climate conditions for the next months and seasons. Results are shown for prediction systems with the best performance (best skill scores).

Decadal predictions

Probabilistic forecasts of climate conditions for the next years. Results are shown for prediction systems with the best performance (best skill scores).

USER GUIDE

LEGEND

PREDICTED TERCILE (tercile plots)

PREDICTED TERCILE (probability maps)

Climate predictions are shown using terciles, which represent three categories - below normal, normal, and above normal - and the probabilities of each category to occur. The most likely tercile refers to the tercile with more probability to occur. The 'normal' category (in grey) refers to the average conditions for a variable or indicator in a particular time of the year. In the past, the probability of each tercile is considered to be the same (that is, one third). This is what we call the climatology.

PREDICTION QUALITY (tercile plots)

No quality forecast (transparency)

PREDICTION QUALITY (probability maps)

X

No quality forecast

No quality forecast means that past predictions were not better than climatology, and it is indicated with a cross on the map. In these cases, the use of the climatology (or business as usual) is recommended. When the prediction has quality, it means that using the prediction is better than using the climatology.

SEASONAL

Prediction System: ECMWF S5 Model start date: March 1st 2025 Calibration method: Quantile mapping Reference dataset: ERA5 Reference period: 1993-2016

FROST DAYS

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

GROWING DEGREE DAYS

High probability of above normal growing degree days in the southern part of Catalunya. Probability of 76% of growing degree days above 92.7°C in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the normal number of growing degree days in March ranges between 67.4 and 92.7°C.

FROST DAYS

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in April in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

GROWING DEGREE DAYS

Enhanced probability of growing degree days generally across Catalunya, with the forecast showing no quality in Raimat. In Raimat, the normal number of growing degree days in April ranges between 67.4 and 92.7°C.

FROST PROTECTION

MARCH - APRIL

Legend

- Most likely tercile
- Below normal
 - Normal
 - Above normal
- x: No quality forecast
- Raimat vineyard

DECADAL

Prediction System: **Multi-model** Model start date: **January 2025** Calibration method: **Quantile mapping** Reference dataset: **ERA5Land** Reference period: **1991-2020**

FROST DAYS

2026 (March-April)

High probability of below normal number of frost days in all the regions of Catalonia.

2027 (March-April)

High probability of below normal number of frost days in all the regions of Catalonia.

Raimat vineyard

Time series showing observations and predictions of frost days in the Raimat vineyard. The normal number of frost days in this period is one. Coloured squares show the predicted most likely tercile whereas black dots are observations.

High probability of below normal number of frost days (zero days) in Raimat vineyard in March-April 2026.

Raimat vineyard

Time series showing observations and predictions of frost days in March-April in the Lleida province, where the Raimat vineyard is located. The normal number of frost days in this period in the Lleida province ranges between 17 and 20. Coloured squares show the predicted most likely tercile whereas black dots are observations.

High probability of below normal number of frost days (zero days) in Raimat vineyard in March-April 2027.

FROST PROTECTION MARCH - APRIL

Legend

- Most likely tercile
- Below normal
 - Normal
 - Above normal
 - No quality forecast
 - Raimat vineyard

DECADAL Prediction System: EC-Earth3 Model start date: January 2024 Calibration method: Simple bias-adjustment Reference dataset: ERA5Land Reference period: 1991-2020

GROWING DEGREE DAYS

2025 (March-April)

High probability of normal growing degree days in the north eastern part of Catalunya. Crosses indicate regions where there is no forecast quality.

2026 (March-April)

High probability of normal growing degree days in the north eastern part of Catalunya and below normal growing degree days in the central area. Crosses indicate regions where there is no forecast quality.

Raimat vineyard

Time series showing observations and predictions of growing degree days in March-April in the Lleida province, where the Raimat vineyard is located. The normal number of growing degree days in this period in the Lleida province ranges between 0 and 0.39 °C. Coloured squares show the predicted most likely tercile whereas black dots are observations.

No quality forecast

The prediction for March-April 2025 does not have enough quality.

Raimat vineyard

Time series showing observations and predictions of growing degree days in March-April in the Lleida province, where the Raimat vineyard is located. The normal number of growing degree days in this period in the Lleida province ranges between 0 and 0.39 °C. Coloured squares show the predicted most likely tercile whereas black dots are observations.

No quality forecast

The prediction for March-April 2026 does not have enough quality.

WATER MANAGEMENT

APRIL - SEPTEMBER

Legend

SEASONAL

Seasonal prediction System: ECMWF S5 Model start date: March 1st 2025 Calibration method: Quantile mapping Reference dataset: ERA5 Reference period: 1993-2016

TOTAL PRECIPITATION

April 2025

slightly higher probability of above normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

May 2025

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

June 2025

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

WATER MANAGEMENT

APRIL - SEPTEMBER

Legend

SEASONAL

Seasonal prediction System: ECMWF S5

Model start date: March 1st 2025

Calibration method: Quantile mapping

Reference dataset: ERA5

Reference period: 1993-2016

TOTAL PRECIPITATION

July 2025

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

September 2025

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

August 2025

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

WATER MANAGEMENT

APRIL - SEPTEMBER

Legend

SEASONAL

Seasonal prediction System: ECMWF S5 Model start date: March 1st 2025 Calibration method: Quantile mapping Reference dataset: ERA5 Reference period: 1993-2016

AVERAGE TEMPERATURE

April 2025

Raimat vineyard

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

June 2025

Raimat vineyard

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

May 2025

Raimat vineyard

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

WATER MANAGEMENT

APRIL - SEPTEMBER

Legend

Most likely tercile (probability)

Below normal (%) Normal (%) Above normal (%)

40 55 70 85 100 >40 40 55 70 85 100

x: No quality forecast Raimat vineyard

SEASONAL Seasonal prediction System: ECMWF S5 Model start date: March 1st 2025 Calibration method: Quantile mapping Reference dataset: ERA5 Reference period: 1993-2016

AVERAGE TEMPERATURE

July 2025

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

August 2025

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

September 2025

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

WATER MANAGEMENT

APRIL - SEPTEMBER

Legend

SEASONAL

Prediction System: ECMWF S5 Model start date: March 1st 2025 Calibration method: Quantile mapping Reference dataset: ERA5 Reference period: 1993-2016

HEATWAVES

July 2025

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

August 2025

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

September 2025

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

ASPECT
FACILITATING RESILIENT CLIMATE ADAPTATION

WATER MANAGEMENT

APRIL - SEPTEMBER

Legend

Most likely tercile: Below normal (light blue), Normal (grey), Above normal (orange)
 x: No quality forecast (light blue), Raimat vineyard (black dot)

DECADAL

Prediction System: Multi-model Model start date: January 2025 Calibration method: Quantile mapping Reference dataset: ERA5Land Reference period: 1991-2020

Legend

TOTAL PRECIPITATION

2026 (April-September)

High probability of above normal precipitation conditions in the north-western and north-eastern regions of Catalunya. Crosses indicate regions where there is no forecast quality.

2027 (April-September)

High probability of above normal precipitation in the northern regions of Catalonia, and high probability of below normal precipitation over the south-western region. Crosses indicate quality where there is no forecast quality.

Raimat vineyard

Time series showing observations and predictions of frost days in April-September in the Raimat vineyard. The normal precipitation in this period in the Raimat vineyard ranges between 32.3 mm/month and 46.1 mm/month. Coloured squares show the predicted most likely tercile whereas black dots are observations.

Poor quality

Above (> 46.06mm/month)
Normal
Below (< 32.29mm/month)

High probability of near normal precipitation (between 32.29 and 46.1 mm/month) in the Raimat vineyard in April-September 2026.

AVERAGE TEMPERATURE

2026 (April-September)

High probability of above normal temperatures in all the northern regions of Catalonia.

2027 (April-September)

High probability of above normal temperatures in all the northern regions of Catalonia.

Raimat vineyard

Time series showing observations and predictions of frost days in April-September in the Raimat vineyard. The normal temperature in this period in the Raimat vineyard ranges between 20.7°C and 21.9°C. Coloured squares show the predicted most likely tercile whereas black dots are observations.

High quality

Above (> 21.95degC)
Normal
Below (< 20.74degC)

High probability of above normal temperature conditions in Raimat vineyard in April-September 2026.

ASPECT
FACILITATING SEAMLESS CLIMATE ADAPTATION

WATER MANAGEMENT

APRIL - SEPTEMBER

Legend

Prediction System: **Multi-model** Model start date: **January 2025** Calibration method: **Variance inflation** Reference dataset: **ERA5Land** Reference period: **1991-2020**

SPEI

2026 (April-September)

High probability of drier than normal conditions in all the regions of Catalonia. Crosses indicate regions where there is no forecast quality.

2027 (April-September)

High probability of drier than normal conditions in all the normal conditions in all the regions of Catalonia.

GROWING DEGREE DAYS

2026 (April-September)

High probability of below normal number of frost days in the northern regions of Catalonia. Crosses indicate regions where there is no forecast quality.

2027 (April-September)

High probability of below normal number of frost days in the northern regions of Catalonia. Crosses indicate regions where there is no forecast quality.

Time series showing observations and predictions of the SPEI6 (April-September accumulation) in the Raimat vineyard. The normal range for the SPEI6 in this period in the Raimat vineyard ranges between -0.46 and 0.47. Coloured squares show the predicted most likely tertile whereas black dots are observations.

Raimat vineyard

Raimat vineyard

High probability of drier than normal conditions in the Raimat vineyard in April-September 2026.

Time series showing observations and predictions of frost days in March-April in the Lleida province, where the Raimat vineyard is located. The normal number of frost days in this period in the Lleida province ranges between 17 and 20. Coloured squares show the predicted most likely tertile whereas black dots are observations.

Raimat vineyard

Raimat vineyard

High probability of below normal number of frost days (less than 17 days) in Lleida in April-September 2025.

Most likely tertile

Below normal Normal Above normal

Below normal Normal Above normal

x: No quality forecast Raimat vineyard

WATER MANAGEMENT

APRIL - SEPTEMBER

Legend

SEASONAL

Prediction System: **ECMWF S5** Model start date: **March 1st 2025** Calibration method: **Quantile mapping** Reference dataset: **ERA5** Reference period: **1993-2016**

GROWING DEGREE DAYS

July 2025

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

August 2025

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

September 2025

Very high probability of below normal number of frost days across Catalunya. Probability of 100% of zero frost days in March in the Raimat vineyard. In Raimat, the below-normal frost days is zero, normal is one, and above-normal is more than one.

7.2. British Red Cross Personas

Further information about personas identified in the British Red Cross, and the aims and necessary features of the website tool for each persona.

AMARI: A responder/ operational manager who doesn't understand climate change or probable impacts on their community, or why it's relevant to their role

Aims:

- Provide an accessible (and not overwhelming) website that will help motivate someone as to why embedding climate into resilience considerations for the future is important.
- Highlight the increasing risk from hot weather.

Necessary features:

- Explainers throughout: What does this mean for you?
- People and community focussed throughout.
- Story and lived experience content.
- Include information about impacts and vulnerability.
- Visually engaging and easy to navigate

BLAIR : Responder / operational manager with no formal climate education but some interest in climate change and impacts

Aims:

- Provide an accessible (and not overwhelming) website to highlight the increasing risk from hot weather.
- Provide the way to access information and tools to help with considering how hot weather events might increase in their response area.

- Highlight some of the climate-related decisions identified during user engagement that they may want to consider.

Necessary features:

- Explainers throughout: What does this mean for you?
- People and community focussed, relatable stories.
- Visually engaging and easy to navigate.

CHARLIE: Experienced responder / operational manager with formal climate education and/or proactive climate interest

Aims:

- Help provide information about (or a reminder of) available tools and resources for accessing information about current and future climate hazards and vulnerability.
- Provide a place that they can signpost other responders to.
- Provide more education around seamless prediction (including current state of limitations) around extreme weather and climate.

Necessary features:

- Explainers throughout (validation): What does this mean for you?
- People and community focussed.
- Comprehensible - not too technical.

DYLAN: Strategic insights team combining complex information from a range of sources

Aims:

- Help provide information about (or a reminder of) available tools and resources for accessing information about current and future climate information.
- Provide more education around seamless prediction (including current state of limitations) around extreme weather and climate including limitations of prediction

research. This provides a starting point for education which, if relevant, more detailed conversations with research scientists in the area can start from.

- Provide a tool for them to use in working with other staff around climate risk, and/or to signpost responders or other British Red Cross staff to for an introductory resource around climate risk

Necessary features: Provide links to tools and data.

EMBER: Strategy Leadership and Senior Decision Makers

Aims:

- Help provide a reminder tool of available tools and resources for accessing information about future hazards and vulnerability.
- Provide a place that they can signpost other members of staff to.
- Provide more education around seamless prediction (including current state of limitations) around extreme weather and climate, including the current limitations of prediction research.

Necessary features:

- Quick and easy to navigate.

7.3. CMCC Governance Case Study Additional Information

7.3.1. Detailed explanation of CMCC Case Study components

In this Annex there is a detailed explanation of each component of the Governance Case Study:

#1- High-resolution convective-permitting climate modelling

Within the High-Resolution Convective-Permitting Climate Modelling component, SMHI and University of Zagreb are developing an Event-Based Downscaling (EBD) framework that targets selected high-impact events such as heavy precipitation events and heatwaves. The scientific rationale is that climate-related damages and adaptation needs are driven by discrete events, while conventional regional climate models (>10 km resolution) cannot adequately represent convective processes or fine-scale spatial features. A key novelty of this approach is the use of kilometre-scale convective-permitting modelling (CPM) with a well-established regional modelling system, Harmonie-Climate (HCLIM), providing high-resolution climate information on extreme events tailored for local users. By combining targeted event detection with 3-km simulations, the method explicitly resolves deep convection, mesoscale circulations, and land-atmosphere interactions, offering a substantial improvement in the realism of extreme events.

To provide seamless climate information, the group utilises the SMHI large ensemble, comprising nearly 100 model years for the early 2000s and 100 model years for the 2040 horizon, all produced with the EC-Earth3 Earth System Model (ESM). These two periods represent present-day and near-future climate conditions (approximately +1°C and +2°C global warming), enabling consistent and robust comparison of extreme events across time. However, this also reflects a key limitation: reliance on a single ESM captures internal variability but not structural uncertainty across models. Other known limitations include dependence on the event detection algorithms, which determine which periods are selected for downscaling, and sensitivity to changes in large-scale atmospheric circulation. As circulation patterns evolve under future climate conditions, analogues from different time periods may be required to adequately represent future extreme events. These issues, along with the single-ESM dependency, will be explicitly documented.

#2 - Downscaling of predictions to regional planning scales

The focus of this section is on statistical downscaling of decadal predictions for the Emilia-Romagna region developed by CMCC Bologna. Statistical downscaling is a mathematical technique which allows to bridge the gap between the comparatively coarse spatial scale typical of climate models and the refined spatial scale required by users. More in detail, the approach adopted is referred to as hybrid statistical-dynamical downscaling. It works in two steps: in the first step, we use observations to establish a statistical relationship between the variable we wish to predict (e.g. precipitation in a small 5-kilometers tile) and some indicator of the large-scale atmospheric circulation. The rationale is that climate models

used to produce decadal predictions are often better able to directly predict the latter than the former. In the second step, the predicted large-scale circulation is fed into the statistical model to obtain a final prediction for the variable of interest.

In plain words, the main goal is to skilfully predict climatic variations of a specific region (Emilia-Romagna), with a spatial granularity sufficient to capture local effects (e.g. individual municipalities), comparatively far ahead in the future (one to a few years ahead). Here, by “climatic variations” we actually mean changes or anomalies in a range of specific indicators (for example, total annual accumulated precipitation) that our end-user has identified as relevant for their activity.

- What are decadal predictions?

Decadal predictions are predictions of the Earth system which extend up to ten years ahead. They are produced operationally by a number of centres across the world, and are feasible due to the influence of certain slowly-evolving components of the Earth’s system on the atmosphere. Compared to weather forecasts, however, the information decadal predictions convey is somewhat diluted: for example, one typically predicts changes in climatic statistics over multi-year periods –for instance, whether a region will experience wetter or drier conditions than normal– rather than precipitation amounts on specific days.

- How do we know predictions are accurate?

Retrospective predictions, or hindcasts, are commonly employed to evaluate the ability of the decadal predictions to match past observations (a.k.a. skill). Hindcasts are generated by predicting past states of the Earth using only information antecedent the forecast period: for instance, decadal predictions for the decade 1971-1980 would be initialised based on observations in November 1970. Whenever we make statements about predictions’ skill, we are referring to the skill of the hindcast predictions pitched against past observations of the climate.

- Why statistical downscaling?

State-of-the-art climate models used to produce decadal predictions have a typical horizontal resolution of approximately 100 kilometers. It means that the climate information they output is averaged in space over square tiles covering the Earth’s surface, where the size of each tile is about 100 km. Often this resolution is too coarse to meet end users’ requirements: more spatial granularity is necessary to capture, say, important topographic or coastal features which may modulate local climate significantly. In this work, we couple decadal predictions with statistical downscaling to overcome this limitation.

- How will this kind of information be delivered?

For this work, we plan to issue predictions by combining plots (e.g. spatial maps of predicted variables in Emilia-Romagna) and explanatory text highlighting the key takeaway points. Predictions will always be accompanied by statements about their ability to predict past states of the climate as measured in hindcast sets.

- Will this help the final user?

Our final user is an environmental protection agency which, amongst several other activities, lends advice to external organisations whose operations are influenced by the climate (often

sectorial governmental authorities or consortia). In this case, therefore, the decision-making chain is complex, ramified, and distributed across multiple entities: the information we plan to provide would enter the decision chain upstream and provide an additional layer of climate content our end-user would leverage and relate to in their interactions with third parties.

#3 - Application of climate projections in hydrological models

Secchia River Basin

The Secchia River basin is located primarily in the Emilia-Romagna region of northern Italy, with smaller portions extending into northern Tuscany. For this study, the focus is on the upper Secchia catchment, defined as the area upstream of the Lugo stream gauge station (10.655°E, 44.433°N), covering approximately 700 km². This outlet was selected because it is relatively unaffected by significant human interventions such as irrigation networks, regulated reservoirs, or intensive groundwater abstractions. Consequently, streamflow at this point is more representative of the basin's natural hydrological response to precipitation and catchment characteristics. This makes it a suitable setting for testing a hydrological model intended to simulate processes such as runoff generation, infiltration, and flow routing under near-natural conditions.

Figure 17. Secchia River Basin

- GEOFRAME

GEOFRAME is a semi-distributed hydrological modeling framework developed by the University of Trento. In a semi-distributed approach, the catchment is divided into interconnected sub-basins or hydrological response units (HRUs), allowing spatial variability in land use, soil types, topography, and meteorological forcing to be represented. While not as detailed as fully distributed models that operate at the grid-cell level, semi-distributed

models offer a practical balance between physical realism and computational efficiency. This makes them particularly suitable for basin-scale simulations of runoff, streamflow, and other hydrological processes in heterogeneous landscapes.

- Input data and HRU definition

GEOFRAME requires daily precipitation and temperature data as input for each sub-basin. These inputs can be provided directly from meteorological stations or interpolated spatially using methods such as kriging to better capture spatial variability. A digital elevation model (DEM) is also required for defining the catchment's topography and drainage network. The DEM supports the delineation of sub-basins and the derivation of geomorphological properties such as slope, flow direction, and flow accumulation, which are critical for hydrological modeling. As optional input, the river network can be used to carve the DEM in order to ensure the simulated river network resembles the natural one. In the case of the Secchia basin, the catchment domain is divided into seven sub-basins, each ranging in area from approximately 70 to 150 km², allowing the model to capture spatial heterogeneity while maintaining computational efficiency.

- Potential Evapotranspiration computation

Net solar radiation is estimated using both shortwave and longwave radiation components, derived from air temperature. For the longwave component, the Idso model is applied. The resulting net radiation is then corrected using the skyview factor, which is obtained from the geomorphological analysis based on the DEM. Once net radiation is available, potential evapotranspiration (PET) can be calculated. GEOFRAME provides multiple PET estimation methods, including the FAO-adjusted Penman-Monteith equation and the Priestley-Taylor method. For this study, the Penman-Monteith FAO-adjusted method was selected for model calibration due to its robustness and suitability for varied climatic conditions. In the case of the Secchia basin, a uniform crop coefficient of 0.65 and a canopy height of 9 meters were applied across the entire model domain.

- ERM model

GEOFRAME incorporates an Embedded Reservoir Model (ERM), which simulates the main components of the hydrological cycle through a series of interconnected modules. These include precipitation, snow accumulation and melt, canopy interception, root zone dynamics, and deep percolation. Each module is characterised by its own set of parameters (18 in total), which are used during model calibration. For the Secchia basin, the model was calibrated over the period 2003–2017 and validated from 2018 to 2023, aligning with the training and testing period used for the machine learning (ML) model. The resulting Kling-Gupta Efficiency (KGE) values were 0.70 for the calibration period and 0.59 for the validation period, indicating good performance, particularly considering the natural flow conditions.

An important thing to note is that, unlike machine learning (ML) approaches that rely solely on streamflow data, GEOFRAME allows for a complete representation of the basin's water balance. It provides internal estimates of variables such as snow water equivalent, groundwater recharge, root zone storage, and the various runoff components, offering a more process-based understanding of hydrological dynamics.

There are 16 different Machine Learning models with various lag time and seasonality impacts which were tested. Based on the results, shown in the following figure, Graph Neural

Network (GNN) performs better than traditional ML techniques. According to different metrics, GNN performed better than Geoframe for streamflow simulation.

Reno Basin

The upper Reno River Basin in northern Italy was selected as the case study and divided into three sub-basins: (i) 1316 is Pracchia, (ii) 2580 is Vergato, and (iii) 4240 is Casalecchio (Figure 23). The catchment area is 1055 km², and its outlet streamflow is measured at the gauge station of Casalecchio di Reno (latitude: 44.47°, longitude: 11.28°).

Figure 23. Study area and location of the streamflow gauge station Casalecchio.

For calibrating the hydrological model, high-resolution gridded meteorological data, called the ERG5 dataset (Antolini et al., 2016), was utilized. The 5-km gridded data of daily precipitation and temperature, developed by ARP Ae-SIMC, was aggregated and averaged for each sub-basin.

- Methodology

A process-based and semi-distributed Hydrological Predictions for the Environment (HYPE, Lindström et al., 2010) model, which was developed by the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI), was used. The precipitation and temperature of three sub-basins were input data of the HYPE model, while the streamflow measured at the Casalecchio station was considered as output data. The calibration period was between 2001 and 2018, while the data from 2019 to 2022 was used for validation.

Different ML models with various lag time and seasonality impacts were tested. Traditional ML models considered in this work include Artificial neural networks, support vector machine, decision tree, random forest, eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), Light Gradient-Boosting Machine (LightGBM), and Category Boosting (CatBoost), and a few more models. Table 1 compares traditional ML models with GNN in hydrological modeling based on different aspects.

Table 1 –Comparison of different traditional ML models with GNN in hydrological modeling

Aspect	Traditional ML models	GNN
Spatial Structure	Not explicitly modeled	Explicitly modeled via graph
Data	Precipitation, temperature	Precipitation, temperature, connection matrix
Type of modeling	Lump hydrological modeling	Semi-distributed hydrology

7.3.2. Detailed explanation of CMCC Case Study prototype

From Global to Local: Downscaling for Planning

Decadal predictions estimate climate conditions 1–5 years ahead. Unlike weather forecasts that predict day-to-day events, decadal predictions provide information over multi-year periods and for specific climate indicators, such as annual precipitation or number of rainy days.

To interpret decadal predictions, we rely on **climatology**, meaning long-term averages of observed climate variables—in this case from 1962 to 2024—mapped at high spatial resolution (5 km).

Because climate models operate on coarse grids (around 100 km), we apply **statistical downscaling** to bridge the gap and obtain local-scale predictions vs forecasts, **translating large-scale model output into information relevant for municipalities**. This step allows us to visualise how predicted anomalies compare with historical norms in specific locations (Figure a and b).

From Global to Local: Downscaling for Planning

Finally, the **skill** component evaluates how reliable these predictions are.

Using hindcasts (retrospective forecasts), we compare past predictions with observations and compute metrics, such as the Pearson correlation (Figure c).

Predictions are only considered trustworthy where hindcasts show significant and consistent skill.

High-resolution convective-permitting climate modelling

Climate extremes—such as heavy rainfall events and tropical nights—are studied using **ensembles**, meaning the same event is simulated many times with slightly different starting conditions. Figure (a) represents the ensemble mean for heavy rainfall in Emilia-Romagna (marked by the red line).

This helps scientists understand not just one possible outcome, but a range of plausible futures. The ensemble mean shows the most likely pattern of the event, while the variation among members helps to estimate the probability that rainfall or temperature will exceed certain thresholds.

b

High-resolution convective-permitting climate modelling

For **heat extremes**, ASPECT also examines tropical nights, when temperatures remain unusually high overnight

Figure (b) compares the conditions around 2000 and 2030 revealing how nighttime heat is intensifying, especially in Bologna urban areas. This is closely linked to the Urban Heat Island effect, where cities retain more heat than surrounding regions, resulting in warmer nights and greater stress for people and infrastructure.

7.4. Case study feedback - additional information

7.4.1. Perceptions of the website aimed at pension trustees gained through survey

Below is additional information provided by the University of Leeds about the survey and initial results.

The organizations represented are primarily based in the United Kingdom (three) and Armenia (one). Three organizations have a longest planning horizon of 2 to 5 years, while the other one plans 5 to 10 years ahead. Three respondents are actuaries and one is an asset manager, all with more than ten years of professional experience in their current roles. All respondents manage global investment portfolios. The funds they are involved with include private-sector pension schemes (3 out of 4) and international organizations (e.g., a United Nations agency or the European Commission). The assets of the largest schemes they are involved with range from approximately €100–500 million (2 out of 4) to over €1 billion. Three of the largest funds are based in the UK, and one is based in Austria. All respondents indicated that their investments are moderately vulnerable to climate-related impacts. Three reported that climate information is used in the investment decision-making process for the largest fund they manage.

After reading the climate information prototype for approximately 5 to 10 minutes, respondents were asked to answer questions assessing its understandability, quality, usability, willingness to share and pay for it, and to provide suggestions for future improvement.

Regarding understandability, all respondents indicated that the balance between text and images in the storyboard was appropriate. However, they did not find the prototype easy to understand: three respondents selected neutral, and one selected hard to understand. Several test questions were also included to evaluate whether respondents correctly understood key concepts, such as climate risk estimation, climatology, predictions, and projections, as well as figures and textual information. Respondents were asked to mark each of seven statements as True, False, or Don't know. Only one respondent answered all statements correctly. As shown in Figure 28, all respondents correctly interpreted the probability of a "1-in-10-year" event. However, understanding of other climate-related concepts, particularly long-term climate projections, was more limited.

Figure 28 Understanding of the information provided in the storyboard

Respondents' perceptions of the quality of this new climate information prototype were explored by asking them to rate their level of agreement with eight quality criteria on a five-point scale, where 1 represents "Strongly disagree," 3 represents "Neither agree nor disagree," and 5 represents "Strongly agree". Figure 29 presents the results. Focusing on the share of respondents who agreed or strongly agreed, the findings indicate the prototype was perceived positively in terms of trustworthiness, accuracy, usability, and format suitability. Respondents expressed opposite opinions regarding its understandability, and showed uncertainty about whether the prototype could be beneficial to themselves, their organizations, or the broader sector.

Figure 29. Perception of the prototype quality

We followed the typology of climate information use proposed by [Jagannathan et al. \(2023\)](#), which identifies six main types: Understand, Motivate & Communicate, Inform, Plan, Fund, and Take Action. Respondents were first asked to indicate the current stage of climate information use within their organizations and then to evaluate the usefulness of the provided climate information prototype for their organizations in each of the six steps on a five-point scale, from “Strongly disagree” to “Strongly agree” plus a “Don’t know / Not applicable” option.

Three out of four respondents indicated that their organizations already use climate information. As shown in Figure 30, all agreed that they use climate information to inform practitioner models or research activities. However, there was no common view regarding the other five types of information use. In particular, none of the respondents reported using climate information to seek funding for adaptation or to evaluate financial implications. Two respondents provided additional details in the following open-ended question. One mentioned that their organization actively integrates climate information into its investment and systematic strategies, for example, in company evaluations and in determining stock weights and exclusions. Another respondent noted that their organization uses climate information for education and modelling purposes.

Figure 30. Current use of weather/ climate information based on typology from [Jagannathan et al. \(2023\)](#)

We then asked respondents to assess the extent to which the provided climate information prototype could help their organizations. Six main types and fourteen sub-types of information use, following [Jagannathan et al. \(2023\)](#), were included in the assessment (see Figure 31). For most categories, respondents selected “Neither agree nor disagree” or “Don’t know/Not applicable,” indicating that they are still uncertain about how this new information could benefit their organizations at this stage. This outcome was expected by the researchers, as the pension sector is still at an early stage of engaging with climate information. One respondent noted that “The industry lacks tangible case studies of the financial materiality of climate impact, especially those that are not abstract in nature. This would be a very tangible, easy-to-understand example. Albeit it is focused on a relatively niche part of asset markets for the average institutional investor.”

Figure 31. Potential use of the provided climate information prototype

Two respondents indicated they were willing to share the climate information prototype internally with their organizations' climate research teams, while only one would share it with external audiences. All four respondents were unsure whether their organizations would be willing to pay for it. The most commonly suggested improvements include making the information easier to access, providing guidance/training on its use, giving more details on reliability, and tailoring the information to their organizations' timescales and specific needs (see Figure 32).

Figure 32. Areas of improvements in the provided climate information prototype

Respondents were also asked to rank the top five sectors of the economy they think will be most affected by physical climate impacts. For analysis, the sector ranked first was assigned a score of 5, while the fifth-ranked sector received a score of 1. Sectors not selected were

assigned a score of 0. Figure 33 presents the average scores for each sector, with error bars indicating standard deviations. All respondents selected the sector “Water supply, sewerage, waste management, and remediation activities”, which also has the highest average score.

Figure 33. Top 5 sectors affected by physical climate impacts

7.4.2. Perceptions of training delivered in financial sector hackathon

In the feedback forms from the hackathon, we received several responses around this training, with 4 out of 9 respondents positively agreeing that this training helped them feel more confident in applying decadal predictions. The raw information received in the feedback form is provided below.

<p>Prior to the ASPECT training (Prof Jason Lowe OBE and Dr Freya Garry), I had limited confidence in using decadal predictions.</p>	<p>Following the ASPECT training (Prof Jason Lowe OBE and Dr Freya Garry), I now feel more confident in applying decadal predictions.</p>	<p>Please share any additional comments about the ASPECT decadal training or other elements of the onboarding and science talks.</p>
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Agree	Agree	a useful range of discussions to prep
Neutral	Neutral	
Neutral	Agree	
Disagree	Neutral	
Agree	Strongly agreed	I really liked the onboarding session, as it paved the way to the baseline of the challenge and the expectations. In addition, it had relevant material to review.
Agree	Neutral	
Disagree	Disagree	
Neutral	Neutral	
Disagree	Agree	

7.4.3. Perceptions of in person training to the British Red Cross

After the in-person event, direct feedback from responders was requested, which elicited the following results. Of the 14 feedback forms received (available scores 1 (not at all) to 5 (extremely)):

How enjoyable did you find these sessions?

Average **4.4 score** (1 scored 3, 6 scored 4, 7 scored 5)

a. Seasonal training

In relation to the training on Seasonal forecasts, how confident were you interpreting seasonal forecasts before the training?

Average **2.4 score** (3 scored 1, 4 scored 2, 6 scored 3, 1 scored 4)

In relation to the training on Seasonal forecasts, how confident are you in interpreting seasonal forecasts now?

Average **4.3 score** (10 scored 4, 4 scored 5)

Increase of 1.9 (~80% increase in confidence on average)

b. Local Authority Climate Service training

In relation to the training on the Local Authority Climate Service, how confident were you using this tool before the training?

Average **1.2 score** (9 scored 1, 3 scored 2)

In relation to the training on the Local Authority Climate Service, how confident are you using this tool now?

Average **3.9 score** (3 scored 3, 10 scored 4, 1 scored 5)

Increase of 2.7 (>200% increase in confidence)

Were you given sufficient opportunity to apply skills and knowledge learnt during the training exercises?

Average **4.3 score** (1 scored 3, 8 scored 4, 5 scored 5)

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